
Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.11 - pea - winter rye relay intercropping

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

In spring, semi-leafless form peas (*Pisum sativum* L.) are sown together with winter rye (*Secale cereale* L.) in the same field. In the year of sowing, the pea is harvested for grain production, rye plays the role of cover crops. The winter rye is harvesting for grain production in the next year.

This technology reduces labor and energy costs, the soil is occupied by plants throughout the vegetation period, pea cultivation technology is optimized (less pathogen spread, better nutrient uptake).

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- | | |
|---|--------------------|
| 1 | rye as cover crops |
| 2 | rye undersowing |
| 3 | NA |
| 4 | NA |
| 5 | |
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

15 - Cover crops

Other one (if any)

27 - Undersowing

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P16 - Lithuania (LAMMC)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Field pea are an important legume in the crop rotation of an organic farm. Farmers face a number of problems in growing semi-leaf peas: poor soil cover in the early stages of growth, spread of weeds, spread of root diseases, harvesting problems etc. It is therefore necessary to apply innovative solutions and improve field pea cultivation technology. Therefore, pea and winter rye relay intercrop technology has been developed, based on positive plant interactions that promote crop self-regulatory functions. Three demonstration studies in farmers’ fields (picture) have shown that the yield of winter rye is not different from that of conventionally grown. It can be argued that nitrogen, light and moisture were better utilized. Pea - winter rye relay intercropping technology lasts for two years (e. g. date of sowing peas and rye 28.04.2018; harvesting of peas 04.08.2018; harvesting of winter rye 05.07.2019). In the first year, peas (0.9-1.0 million seeds ha⁻¹) and winter rye (0.4-0.5 million seeds ha⁻¹) are sown in spring. Growth and development of field pea are normal during the first sowing year. But winter rye grows only vegetative mass and usually reaches the tillering stage (BBCH30-31). Winter rye provides good weed control and phytosanitary protection of the soil. Winter rye might, also suppress field peas. Therefore, it is worth to carry out more detailed studies on the seed rates of pea and winter rye. During harvesting, pea straw is chopped and spread in the field, and winter rye is shortened in the same time. The mulching of winter rye is done in the second half of September. Two mulches are also possible, depending on meteorological conditions and growth intensity. Mulching encourages winter rye for tillering. At the time when winter rye cultivation was followed by peas, soil ploughing resulted in higher mineralization of the incorporated organic

matter and mineral N content and its migration to deeper soil layers. Pea-winter rye relay intercropping technology saves energy and labour costs.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Rye (*Secale cereale* L.) winter form, grows < 2000 m above sea level, resistant to -25 oC (to -35 oC depending on the thickness of the snow cover) temperature in winter.

Field Pea (*Pisum sativum* L. (Partim) – grows <900 m above sea level.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Less favorable conditions for the cultivation of peas are: pH <6,0, clay content in the soil <20 %; uncompressed, non-soaking, non-stony soils

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain

2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect

Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

Aziz M. , Mahmood A., Asif M. and Ali A. 2015. Wheat – based intercropping: a review. *The Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 25(4): 2015, Page: 896-907

Joseph K.X., Yaro R. N., Soyel J.K., Kofi E.S., Ghaney P. 2018. Role of Intercropping in Modern Agriculture and Sustainability: A Review. *British Journal of Science*, Vol. 16 (2):67-75

Feng L, Raza MA, Chen Y, Khalid MHB, Meraj TA, Ahsan F, et al. (2019) Narrow-wide row planting pattern improves the light environment and seed yields of intercrop species in relay intercropping system. *PLoS ONE* 14(2): e0212885. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0212885>

Wezel A., Casagrande M., Celette F., Vian J-F., Ferrer A. et al.. *Agroecological practices for sustainable agriculture. A review. Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, Springer Verlag/EDP Sciences/INRA, 2014, 34 (1), pp.1-20. [ff10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7). [ffhal-01234800f](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7)

Joseph K.X., Yaro R. N., Soyel J.K., Kofi E.S., Ghaney P. 2018. Role of Intercropping in Modern Agriculture and Sustainability: A Review. *British Journal of Science*, Vol. 16 (2):67-75

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

Yin W., Chai Q., Zhao C., Yu A., Fan Z., Hu F., Fan H., Guo Y., Coulter J. A. 2020. Water utilization in intercropping: A review, *Agricultural Water Management*, Volume 241, 106335, ISSN 0378-3774, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2020.106335>

Impacts

Knörzer H., Graeff-Hönninger S., Guo B., Wang P., Claupein W. (2009) The Rediscovery of Intercropping in China: A Traditional Cropping System for Future Chinese Agriculture – A Review. In: Lichtfouse E. (eds) Climate Change, Intercropping, Pest Control and Beneficial Microorganisms. Sustainable Agriculture Reviews, vol 2. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2716-0_3

Joseph K.X., Yaro R. N., Soyel J.K., Kofi E.S., Ghaney P. 2018. Role of Intercropping in Modern Agriculture and Sustainability: A Review. British Journal of Science, Vol. 16 (2):67-75

Feng L, Raza MA, Chen Y, Khalid MHB, Meraj TA, Ahsan F, et al. (2019) Narrow-wide row planting pattern improves the light environment and seed yields of intercrop species in relay intercropping system. PLoS ONE 14(2): e0212885. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0212885>

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.12 - Field margins strip to improve soil quality

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Flowering annual and perennial herbaceous species combinations in field margins, which is suitable to improve soil parameters not only attract pollinator insects in intensive farming conditions.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Field margins
 - 2 Wildflower strips
 - 3 flower mixes strip
 - 4 Insect trap crops
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected

Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Yes
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

6 - Semi-natural habitat creation and enhancement

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P16 - Lithuania (LAMMC)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early adopters
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The compaction is the result of working with heavy machinery with narrow tires, especially on the edges of the field when agricultural machinery drives several times through the same place. The soil at the edge of the field is compressed, cracks appear, the seed bed is poorly prepared and the plants germination is not homogeneous. The consequence of this process is the empty and weedy edges of the agricultural fields, the lower the yield of the crops. Also, it can be caused due to biological reasons: lack of crop diversification in the crop rotation, low soil organic matter content. Low plant diversity, the availability of nutrients from subsoil in chemical fields is limited due to higher soil density, lower oxygen content and microbiological activity. The goal of the plant mixtures is to determine annual and perennial herbaceous species combinations in field margins, which might be suitable to improve soil parameters not only attract pollinator insects in intensive farming conditions. We recommend to involve N-fixing legumes, deep-rooted plants, C-accumulating plants, plants with high underground mass and nutrient mobilization, and plants with allelopathic properties in these mixtures. Short-lived plants for mixtures are suitable: yellow sweet clover (*Melilotus officinalis* L.), white sweetclover (*Melilotus albus* L.), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), buckwheat (*Fagopyrum tataricum* L.), radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.), phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* L.) and other. Differently from plant mixtures to attract pollinators, C-accumulating plants are also needed here (e. g. black oat (*Avena strigosa* Schreb.), annual ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.) and other. Perennial legume swards have a very strong positive effect on the soil such as lucerne (*Medicago sativa* L.), esparsette (*Onobrychis viciifolia* Scop.), red clover (*Trifolium pratense*

L.), Birdsfoot trefoil (*Lotus pedunculatus* Cav. etc.). The mixtures of legume with grasses greatly improve the accumulation of organic matter in the soil.

Studies have shown that the cultivation of herbaceous flowers plants in the strips reduces soil density, increases overall porosity, improves soil structure, and improves the stability of structural aggregates. This means that a sustainable soil structure is formed at the field margins, which ensures optimal air and water regime, availability of nutrients to plants and soil biota. Farmers' point of view, tends to be positive on this flowering strip practice. Mostly the case for agronomical and ecological processes, like pollination and animal pest control. The influence of flower strips on the farmer's economical balance and social recognition are still large gaps. Need more information for farmers, can lead to a higher uptake of flower strips in farming.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

This practice is very flexible, elements can be selected for different soil structure and meteorological conditions in the area of the practice application. The negative effects of higher temperatures and amount of precipitation depends on the proportion of semi-natural habitats within a site.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

All soil types are suitable for this practice. It is important to choose the right element of the practice (plant species, etc.). However, lack species associated with very acid or base-rich soil. Also, potassium and magnesium deficiency resulting from repeated hay cutting and removal appeared to restrict the diversity of species on some semi-natural sites.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

Alexandra D. Papanikolaou, Ingolf Kühn, Mark Frenzel, Oliver Schweiger. Semi-natural habitats mitigate the effects of temperature rise on wild bees. 2017. Vol.54 (2): 345-679 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12763>

Farming systems

Holland, J.M., Douma, J.C., Crowley, L. et al. Semi-natural habitats support biological control, pollination and soil conservation in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 37, 31 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0434-x>

Julie Larkin, Helen Sheridan, John A. Finn, Hannah Denniston, Daire Ó hUallacháin. Semi-natural habitats and Ecological Focus Areas on cereal, beef and dairy farms in Ireland, *Land Use Policy*, Volume 88, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104096>

Limiting soil factors

A. R. McCrea, I. C. Trueman, M. A. Fullen (2004) Factors relating to soil fertility and species diversity in both semi-natural and created meadows in the West Midlands of England. *European Journal of Soil Science*. Vol 55 (2): 335-348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2004.00606.x>

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
-

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.16 - Three new species of triticale (X. Triti- cosecale Wittm.) at Szeged, in Hungary, with 'added values'

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The cultivation and use of triticale juice may come at a turning point, a change of era. The latest varieties of Cereal Research Non-Profit Ltd. in Szeged have excellent productivity, and their cultivation is economical and there are new possibilities for human use. The targeted boost of animal husbandry and breeding will increasingly require cheap, high-yielding and high-biological-value feed, for which triticale juice can serve as an excellent commodity base. In recent years, the National Agricultural Variety Classification Commission has qualified 3 new varieties bred in Szeged, which represent one or more special agronomic traits, using the now fashionable term "added values". With their economic characteristics, these varieties serve as a significant biological basis for Hungarian plant production.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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2
3

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4
5
—

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

15 - Cover crops

Other one (if any)

22 - Intercropping

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P12 - Hungary (MTA ATK)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Yes

Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	few farmers (“innovators”)

Specificities or further description of the practice

In triticale, our GK Maros variety leads the seed market, and GK Szemes is in second place. A new, starting variety is GK Temes, an assimilating, green-stemmed type and, due to this feature, it tolerates heat shock days excellently, it is able to produce high yields even under stressful conditions GK has received several awards in recent years for the breeding results of this species: the OMÉK Crop Production Award, and then they were included in the TOP 100 innovations of Hungary in 2019.

GK Temes’s genetic productivity is outstanding: in the 3-year experiments of NÉBIH it exceeded the average of the standard varieties by 6%. Resistant to major fungal diseases, good weed suppressor. It is therefore an excellent drought-tolerant variety suitable for organic production.

Italy Business experiments (Agr. Mana Stefano, Genola (CUNEO)), the biomass production of the Spanish triticale varieties GK Rege and Forricale, a control variety already used for this purpose, was tested on a 3x5 ha plot. The varieties were sown on 28 October and harvested as above-ground biomass on 12 May at early milk maturity. In the trial, the GK Rege variety performed outstandingly with a green biomass yield of 62 t/ha at 30% dry matter content. The Spanish variety used as a control finished well behind it, yielding 26.5%, certainly setting a European record in the Po Valley. A healthy product was described, with no problems with drooping, but also with very tall stems and dense foliage. The biomass production was excellent!

Opinions:

Hungary has an ECO seed database, where the data of organic seeds are available in Hungary and their suppliers.

Opinions from Slovenia experts: Besides our meat industry activities, we also have significant livestock and crop production activities.

In a pig feeding, fodder produced in our own areas is important. Part of the land is poor, exposed, sandy land and that is why we consider it important to grow crops that can be grown on such soils and can give a good yield. They consider the variety Maros triticale from Grain Research GK Maros to be such an innovation. It can also grow well in problematic, nutrient-poor soils. In the last season, we were able to achieve a yield of 5.5 t/ha on an area of about 80 ha, even in poorer soil conditions. It is characterised by good protein content, high nutritional value, excellent cultivability and economical production.

2- The GK Szemes tritikále variety has been in the seed rotation for a long time. It is grown in less well-endowed parts of the farm and the experience shows that this variety can also perform very well on these fields. For the species, GK Szemes has a fast and vigorous germination rate, rapid initial development and excellent winter hardiness. It is not susceptible to disease and can be grown safely with simple crop protection. In our soil and climatic conditions, it can produce a stable yield of 7 t/ha.

3- GK Semy triticale is growing in Slovenia for many years. It is a very good variety because it does not need to be sown early and can be harvested much earlier than other triticale varieties. There have been years when we have followed it up with a second crop of maize and it has also been able to mature. We have also tried to use

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

GK Temes, an assimilating, green-stemmed type and, due to this feature, it tolerates heat shock days excellently, it is able to produce high yields even under stressful conditions. (www.gabonakutato.hu)

The GK Temes variety is heavily waxy and green-stemmed, making it an excellent drought and heat stress tolerant variety with good adaptability. It is an excellent bush grower with good weed suppression, making it suitable for biofertilization. The plant is characterised by high yield stability and the ability to assimilate for a very long time, remaining on green stems even after watering and after full ripening. This is the basis of the protection mechanism against heat shock, the continuous assimilation and the slow water loss, which prevents the eyes from drying out. This advantageous trait is also combined with high fungal disease resistance, so that this variety will also produce a firm and healthy green mass by mid-May if sown for mass feeding in October. (GK Híradó, pg. 20.)

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

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Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

It has won the Hungarian Innovation Award of Agriculture on 20th of August in 2021.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

/

Impacts

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Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.17 - Added-value compost

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Added-value compost comprises the incorporation of a beneficial microorganism (e.g. *Trichoderma harzianum*) with biological control activity to improve soil quality (physical, chemical and biological properties). Potential added-value benefits of this compost include suppressiveness or capacity for plant pathogen control, biofertilization, and biostimulation, minimizing the application of chemical fertiliser and pesticides.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 advanced compost
 - 2 particularized compost
 - 3 tailored compost
 - 4 stabilised organic compost
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected

Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

9 - Integrated pest management

Other one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP20 - Spain (CSIC-IRNASA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The use of composts in horticulture and agriculture as growing media can reduce the use of peat, which is a non-renewable resource. Suppressiveness composts have been commonly used to control plant diseases caused by soil-borne pathogens, such as *Pythium* spp., *Fusarium* spp. or *Phytophthora* spp. The incorporation of *Trichoderma harzianum* not only increased the biocontrol capacity of this compost, but also induced changes in the biotic and abiotic characteristics of the compost (Blaya et al., 2013). Potential added-value benefits of particularized compost have been highlighted, and these include suppressiveness or capacity for plant pathogen control, biofertilization, and biostimulation (Cataldo et al., 2021; Hernandez-Lara et al., 2022; Sachdev and Singh, 2020). This added value is an important point in relation to the framework of organic agriculture because the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides is limited. Lopez-Mondejar et al. (2010) found that the combination of citrus compost with *Trichoderma harzianum* could totally or partially substitute peat in crops, making it possible to minimise the application of chemical fertiliser and pesticides.

The addition of species of *Trichoderma* to compost is a widespread technique used to control different plant diseases. The biological control activity of these species is mainly attributable to a combination of several mechanisms of action, which may affect the microbiota involved in the suppressiveness of compost. The higher degree of compost suppressiveness achieved after the addition of *Trichoderma harzianum* may be due not only to its biocontrol ability, but also to changes promoted in both abiotic and biotic characteristics of the growing media (Blaya et al., 2013). The ability of vineyard pruning waste compost, amended (GCTh) or not

(GC) with *T. harzianum*, to suppress *Fusarium* was evaluated and a high relative abundance of certain chitinolytic bacteria as well as in remarkable protection against *Fusarium oxysporum* comparable to that induced by compost without *Trichoderma harzianum* was reported (Blaya et al. 2013).

The addition of vineyard compost supplemented with the beneficial microorganism *Trichoderma harzianum* isolate T-78 to saline soils (NaCl) was studied to determine the impact on soil microbiology, which is the key to restore and rehabilitate degraded soils. The use of vineyard composts supplemented with strain T-78 favoured the development of microbial populations thereby recovering soil microbiota. The method is simple, with a low cost and is highly sustainable—avoiding the use of chemicals such as fertilizers. As *T. harzianum* strain T-78 is salt tolerant, increasing the relative abundance of this specific strain contributed to the rehabilitation of saline soils (Mbarki et al., 2017).

Trichoderma harzianum T-78 enriched compost was assayed as growing medium and organic amendment by testing the biostimulant, biofertilizer and suppressive effect on melon crop. At natural field conditions, the amendment into soil of this advanced compost reduced natural infection percentage on melon plants and increased melon yields. Furthermore, muskmelon plants grown previously sowed on the above compost combination showed lower pathogen incidence and higher melon yield than plants grown on traditional peat plus *T. harzianum* T-78. Therefore, this advanced composting process would be able to permit a more environmental respectful crop production with less chemical inputs (Pascual et al., 2017, 2018).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	NA

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

The addition of species of beneficial microorganisms as *Trichoderma* (biocontrol agent) to organic compost produce benefits in the soil-crop system such as improvement of arid soil quality and saline soil quality (rehabilitation of saline soils), increase of soil fertility, biopesticide effect in soil, nutriactive and biocontrol effect (biological control) of fungal diseases in different horticultural crops by suppression of phytopatogens, reduction of the use of peat as growth media, reduction of fungicide application, biostimulant and biofertilizer effect, increase of crop yield, use of less chemical inputs, increase of soil carbon and nutrient content, and changes of the bacterial community structure and diversity.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

Lopez-Mondejar, R., Bernal-Vicente, A., Ros, M., Tittarelli, F., Canali, S., Intrigiolo, F., Pascual, J.A., 2010. Utilisation of citrus compost-based growing media amended with *Trichoderma harzianum* T-78 in *Cucumis melo* L. seedling production. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 3718–3723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.12.102>

Mbarki, S., Cerdà, A., Brestic, M., Mahendra, R., Abdelly, C., and Pascual, J. A. (2017) Vineyard Compost Supplemented with *Trichoderma Harzianum* T78 Improve Saline Soil Quality. *Land Degrad. Develop.*, 28: 1028– 1037. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2554>

Morales A.B, Bustamante. M.A., Marhuenda-Egea F.C., Moral R., Ros M., Pascual J.A., 2016. Agri-food sludge management using different co-composting strategies: study of the added value of the composts obtained, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 121, 186-197, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.02.012>

Pascual J.A., Bernal-Vicente A., Martinez-Medina A., Ros M., Sánchez C. 2017. Biostimulant and suppressive effect of *Trichoderma harzianum* enriched compost for melon cultivation from greenhouse nursery to field production. *Acta Horticulturae*,1164, 225-231. DOI: 10.17660/ActaHortic.2017.1164.29

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information ('.docx')

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos ('.txt')

- [empty] ...
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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.18 - “By-products Recirculation Units in the Alqueva multipurpose enterprise (EFMA)”- URSA Project

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The URSA (Alqueva by-products recirculation units) project aims to create a network of units (on the irrigated area of Alqueva – MDS, PT), for collection, treatment and transformation (composting) of agricultural by-products into organic fertilizer, that in turn, will be delivered to farmers, for agricultural use, in exchange for their by-products. The valorisation of the organic by-products of agriculture by composting, which produce an organic fertilizer that will be used by farmers enhancing soil quality, protecting water and promoting the efficient use of resources using circular economy in the agricultural context.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

—
1
2
3
4
5
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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P19 - Portugal (INIAV)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected

Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected
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Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

This practice creates units for the valorisation of agricultural and agro-industrial by-products, through a composting process, which produces an organic fertilizer, that is delivered to farmers in exchange for their agricultural by-products. It is currently underway with the implementation of the first URSA unit at Herdade da Abóbada (Serpa). In this unit, there are 18 companies and farmers’ associations associated and this is important for the success of URSA, since the delivery of organic by-products for composting depends on farmers’ adherence. In a near future, a network of units in all Alqueva irrigation area will be created. The main operations, technical coefficients, and duration involved in the composting unit are described as follows:

1. By-products are received, weighted and characterized (olive and vine leaves and branches, corn straw/stubble, grape stalk, bagasse and algae from cleaning irrigation channels),
2. Temporarily stored,
3. Crushing of coarse vegetable by-products (1day/month),
4. Mixing the various elements in the preestablished proportion based on the initial characterization. Alignment in piles, in the open air, each one with horizontal semi-cylindrical structure, with 3m width x 200m long x 2m initial height. Volume of 800 m³, which corresponds to 680tons per pile (average density of 0.85). C/N between 18 and 45 (5 days/month).
5. Promotion of the composting process, with watering and aeration.

Moisture content 50% to 70% and oxygen > 5%; temperature to be reached: 60°C to 70°C for 10 days; aeration and watering carried out with mechanical overturning of each pile (aerated based on needs, in average once each 15 days); Each turner has an output of 200-300m of piles per hour (50 to 90 days). The liquid compound purges by gravity from the piles and stored in a lower plane. 6. Compost removal to a covered space for cooling and stabilization (2 days/month). 7. Screening to remove coarse material (5days/month). 8. Production of pellets (optional) but strongly favouring agricultural use with conventional equipment (5 days/month).9. Analytical characterization and weighing at exit (variable and seasonal).

It is expected that the compost is finished in 110 days, allowing 3 production cycles per year. According to the area per unit, the production of 16 piles per cycle is considered feasible. The monitoring of SOM in Alqueva indicates contents less than 1%. This practice intends to return to the soil the nutrients that are being removed through agriculture, reducing the need for fertilization, improving soil properties and increasing the profitability of crops. The benefits of this practice are the utilisation of by-products from the region, which currently has little or no appreciation, carrying out its conversion to a solid or liquid fertilizer with high market value for farmers, in a controlled and technical way, without excessive economic and environmental costs. This practice gives a sustainable fate to by-products produced in the region and materializes circular economy in agriculture and helps to reduce the environmental and water footprint. Also, creates a service for farmers and reduces their costs of disposal of by-products and acquiring fertilizers. Alqueva has 120,000 hectares of irrigated agriculture, from which 500,000 tons of agricultural or agro-industrial by-products may result per year. For each ton of by-products that URSA values, 100kg of mineral fertilizers (10kg of N), 100 m³ of natural gas, 28670 L of water and 750 kg of CO₂ will be saved.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors needed to create the compost at the URSA units:

Rainfall or irrigation is needed to maintain the compost at the appropriate moisture content = 50 to 70%.

Air temperature too low can make it more difficult to reach temperatures between 60 and 70 °C for 10 days in the compost to disinfect the material.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : If the organic soils/peatlands are facing degradation of their SOM, the application of compost can improve soils fertility. Although, the creation of such an elaborated scheme of URSA units that requires the involvement of farmers and irrigation districts in a network, has high costs of investment that have to be taken into account.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Uncertain
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

A limitation of the application of this practice is the distance that the farmers have to travel to deliver the by-products and collect the compost from the URSA units. Alqueva multipurpose enterprise (EFMA) refers that the ideal distance to a URSA unit is 5 km. Another limitation of the URSA units is the costs required to create the constellation of units and the number of farmers and other actors to associate with these services in order to make it possible. Other limitations might be the type of by-products of an agricultural region and their ability to originate a good quality compost. According to EFMA, a conversion based on the formula 10:RC/N, for example: who delivers by-products with a C/N ratio of approximately 20 will have an exchange of 1:2 (i.e., delivers 2 tons of by-product and receives 1 ton of compost), discounting moisture variations.

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

The URSA units have the following aims:

- Rehabilitation of soil as quality agricultural support and as a filtering barrier;
- Favour the efficient use of water and nutrients, reducing the global needs;
- Reduce the use of mineral fertilizers and increase agricultural profitability;
- Greater soil cohesion, less vulnerable to erosion and desertification;
- Conservative circular use of organic by-products produced in EFMA;
- Water quality and less susceptibility to invasive aquatic species;
- Promotion of soil life and soil fertility;

- Carbon sequestration in soil, as opposed to burning, with reduction of the emission of greenhouse gases.

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.23 - Spreading of gypsum

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Spreading of gypsum to minimize soil erosion and the losses of phosphorus bound to soil and dissolved phosphorus from field to surface water as well as to improve the soil structure.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 gypsum
 - 2 gips
 - 3 kipsi
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	Soil amendment

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

2 - Organic Farming

Other one (if any)

46 - No till

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P9 - Finland (LUKE)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early adopters
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

1. What are the main characteristics/ elements of the practice (including technical specifications)?

Gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is calcium sulfate in terms of its chemical composition, and sulfate is a form of sulfur available to crops. It also contains water of

crystallisation and moisture bound to the surface of particles. Gypsum dissolves in soil water, increasing its salinity, or its ionic strength when speaking in the language of chemistry.

Gypsum is a by-product of phosphoric acid manufacturing, and smaller volumes are generated in flue gas scrubbing at coal-fired power stations. The majority of gypsum spread on Finnish fields comes from Yara’s Siilinjärvi plant. Gypsum is also excavated at mines in other countries.

2. What are the purposes/ functions of the practice?

Gypsum spread on the surface soil layer reduces erosion and the losses of phosphorus bound to soil and dissolved phosphorus. In addition to its impact on water protection, some farmers who have used gypsum have also found improvements in the soil structure. Gypsum improves the soil structure more effectively the more clayey the soil is.

Gypsum adds calcium to soil, forming bridges between soil particles. Calcium and the sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) contained by gypsum increase the ionic strength of the soil solution. Increased ionic strength of the soil solution makes the hydration hull around particles thinner, and particles can move closer to each other. The closer proximity allows multivalent cations, such as Ca^{2+} , to form bridges between particles, thus starting aggregation of particles.

3. What major activities/ inputs are needed to establish/ maintain the practice?

Gypsum can be spread using spreading equipment for moist lime or manure. The spreading of gypsum should take place during crop rotation so that the soil can be lightly tilled after spreading. The established amount for the use of gypsum in water protection is four tonnes per hectare. If necessary, the treatment can be renewed after a few years. Gypsum spreading is not recommended in catchments discharging into lakes or in groundwater areas.

The best time for spreading gypsum is in the autumn after harvesting. Parcels to be sown in the autumn should be tilled after the spreading of gypsum. Perennial crops can only be treated with gypsum in conjunction with regeneration.

When gypsum is delivered, it should be ensured that parcels and roads have a sufficient load-carrying capacity for lorries. Once gypsum has been delivered, it should be spread as quickly as possible. If this is not possible, the pile should be covered with a tarpaulin, as gypsum may form clumps when wet.

4. What are the benefits/ impacts of the practice?

Gypsum decreases soil erosion and the losses of phosphorus bound to soil and dissolved phosphorus. In addition, it reduces the losses of dissolved and particulate organic carbon into water bodies. Considering the soil structures, it is important that the carbon is retained in the field.

5. What do farmers like / dislike about the practice?

As a soil improvement agent, gypsum is one way to retain nutrients in the field.

According to the Sugar Beet Research Centre's studies, gypsum reduces the incidence of sugar beet root rot.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The best spreading time is during autumn just before tillage. The soil should be dry during spreading and it should not rain before tilling the gypsum into the soil.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : It is suitable for clay soils but there is not information available on organic soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil properties do not limit the application of gypsum. However, the soil must be dry enough to decrease compaction of soil during spreading and to allow soil tillage after gypsum spreading.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No

2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect

Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	No Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Adverse Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.24 - Spot spraying

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Rational use of pesticides by spraying only the desired target (via a tractor-sprayer).

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	On-board recognition and precision of herbicide application
2	
3	
4	
5	

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected

 NA

 NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

11 - Precision of herbicide application

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P5 - Belgium (Wallonia) (CRAW)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not applied
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

It is basically enhanced smart spraying. Indeed, this practice is in its essence smart spraying of pesticides in the sense that it is based on the use of an automatic, or, assisted driven tractor pesticide sprayer (both automatic and assisted designates almost the same thing except that it is respectively, either with the use of RTK technology (Real-time Kinematic positioning), or of GPS-RTK technology (a Global Navigation Satellite Systems receiver that is capable of RTK)). But the novelty consists in the adding of optical sensors (cameras), mounted on this assisted or automatic driven tractor-sprayer. These sensor are able to detect either shapes, or colors (wavelengths). They are linked to a console managed by an AI (Artificial Intelligence). And, while familiarizing with a crop field, the AI is able to learn by itself, with data and time (it is typically a learning about recognizing the crop and the crop's weeds in every different climatic and vegetative developmental conditions), and will ultimately be able to recognize precisely and in real time weeds in this crop (i.e identify and differentiate weeds from crop and weeds from naked soil). The end goal is that, once the AI is performing enough on one crop, at the same moment the attached sensors will recognize a weed, the AI will send an order to the tractor-sprayer which will in return autonomously treat the weed and only the weed by controlling individually each nozzle of the sprayer boom, all in a few seconds.

The AI-sensor technology is still in development at CRA-W as of now (July 2021). The currently developed sensor in itself is an optical sensor as mentioned, but in the future it

perfectly could be another type of sensor. Also we may note that, the targets investigated in the development of this technology are essentially weeds, but in the future it perfectly could be fungal pests (by recognizing and treating only sick leaves in vineyards for example) or insects pests (like aphids for example). The purpose of this practice/technology is to localize to an unprecedented level the application of pesticides onto a crop, while maintaining a large scale spraying capacity. So, in addition to being able to spray as much as possible in as little time as possible, with this technology we are able to not spray the entirety of the crop surface. Thus we would make (in all relativity) pesticides savings and also make the soil suffer less from the negatives aspects pesticides may have on it. In order to be applied, this practice requires not any less than to have at disposal a tractor-sprayer, plus the innovative console and sensors. It then subsequently means that one vital prerequisite for this practice is the same as for the use of the ‘‘classical’’ smart spraying practice : we need a good enough network coverage in order to have a strong enough signal for the RTK or GPS-RTK technology to work correctly. Apart from that, the AI-console is not more complex to use than any other ‘‘classical console’’ a farmer may have to deal with. But old farmers in Wallonia (50+ y) may be refractory to it, as they usually are to new technology in general. Another big barrier we could anticipate for farmers, may be that currently the sensor is extremely expensive to manufacture (it is almost the same as buying a second tractor-sprayer). Though, we could argue that this latter issue ultimately would depend on market regulation and policy settings, to modulate the price and/or the accessibility for farmers to the technology.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The limitations are the same than for classical pulverization, i.e for example we may not spray if too much wind, or if there is rain, etc.

There are well known good pulverization practices to respect when it comes to limiting climatic factors and the AI-console in itself doesn't add limitations to these.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : Theoretically it is not a problem. As long as the soil structure permits the use of a tractor-sprayer, then the AI-console can adapt itself. The only thing to take into account may be that the AI-console has to be calibrated to the soil color. Indeed, soils in Wallonia and organic soils as Chernozem (for example) don't have the same color. So, as the AI-console is developed in Wallonia, with Wallonia soils, in order to be used on Chernozem soils (for example) this last will have to recognize a Chernozem soil as being a soil. And that is just a matter of settings and data learning.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No. Not due to the AI-console.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Climatic conditions are relatively not influencing the use of the AI-console, but we may note that if it is so, it is because these last are taken into account in the device functioning. Indeed, weather has an impact on the quality of the optical detection of the sensor, for example : if the foliage is wet it is harder for optical detection because the sunlight is reflected in a different fashion than it would with a non-wet foliage. Or also, shading is a challenge for optical detection because the wavelength of the detection target changes. That explains the importance of the learning process : the AI-console must be able to recognize that a weed is still a weed even if it is shaded or wet for example.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

It might not work in 2.2.2 / 2.2.3 land-use categories because of the sprayer that will most certainly be blocked by trees, not because of the AI-console. Still, it is theoretically doable (see below in this text box for further explications). However, orchards are not usually sprayed.

It is uncertain with 2.4 / 2.4.1 because having multiple crops complicates a lot the algorithm : in addition to what it normally has to do, the AI would have to distinguish crops between them. It will have to be tested on field first.

Rice fields are generally not sprayed with pesticides because then there will be an unmanageable water contamination problem. Even though there was not this contamination problem the practice would not work either in rice fields, nor in permanently irrigated land, due this time to the AI-console. Indeed, the latter is less likely to work properly in a very wetty biotope because there is much sunlight reflection which complicates a lot the optical detection process.

The practice is theoretically applicable in all European farming systems, though it is less likely to be use by any extensive-type farming system. It will rather be more compatible with intensive-type systems because on one hand, of the expensiveness of the AI-console, and on the other hand, of the relevance of utilization of it. Indeed, the AI-console spraying technology is not relevant for all types of crops nor for all type of weeds. Typically this technology works well to treat weeds with a well developed vegetative system (hence that are easily noticeable by the AI-console), like thistle in a maize crop. But with creeping weeds-like or with a pre-emergence-type weed treatment for example, this technology won't be of any use. Because either the AI-console cannot actually see and distinguish the weed, either the way the treatment is processed makes it a nonsense to use a tractor-sprayer.

Theoretically this practice is applicable to organic farming as long as it is a very specific crop-type, for example.

For conservation agriculture it is doable, but would be a total nonsense to spray pesticides in such an agronomic philosophy scheme.

In agro-forestry systems it is also theoretically doable, but the sprayer arms would have to be able to pass in-between trees. A machine which can be invented/tested but has not yet been. Also, if we were to test this practice in agroforestry, a going forward potentially big issue in this particular situation could be that the projected shadow of the trees might impede the image capture and therefore the quality of the detection by the AI-console.

Terrace farming is a-priori totally incompatible with tractor-sprayer usage.

Limiting soil factors

According to FAO, the maximum possible slope for the use of a tractor-sprayer is 15%.

Soil challenges

When exclusively talking about the AI-console - which is all the novelty here - well it helps in no respects to address these soil challenges.

Except for avoiding contamination and enhancing soil biodiversity challenges where we could argue that, localizing and ultimately reducing the total output of pesticides sprayed might contribute in positively.

Indeed, regarding avoiding contamination challenge, what we can say for sure is that it strongly depends on the pesticide used, some pesticides are degraded by UVs (and therefore do not contaminate groundwater), meanwhile for some other pesticides that contaminate a lot groundwater there is a real interest in this technology.

But regarding enhance soil biodiversity challenge, it is more of a mitigated observation : it depends on the weeds detection rate by the AI. Indeed, if it turns out that the crop field is in the end strongly infested by weeds (i.e lots of weeds in each plots of the field), then the smart spraying will look like a spraying in full. Which means soil biodiversity will be impacted almost the same than when spraying in full.

Impacts

Impacts on crop yield :

What is for sure, is that there is a neutral effect : a stabilization of the yield. But, going forward we will have to evaluate if the reduction/limitation of the phytotoxicity effects of some pesticides on some crops (as chicory where this effect is quite remarkable for example), by localizing the spraying may benefit the yields. And in which extent it might do so.

Impacts on farm profitability :

This issue is at study and the data cannot be yet communicated for legal reasons. But what we can already say is that the savings we were to make by pouring, therefore buying less pesticides, are very low likely to compensate the buying of the AI-console in a short/mid-term fashion. Though, at a long-term perspective it might be interesting, but all of this is still being evaluated... Also, the key issue remains that at the moment, at the european level, this AI-console technology is a monopoly market with only 2 or 3 manufacturers able to produce it, let alone sell it (that's a big part as of why it costs so much to invest in). So we will have to wait and see if and when this technology breaks through, and is popularized, how its price will evolve.

Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.25 - Regenerative agriculture in almond farms

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Regenerative agriculture in almond farms includes a combination of reduced tillage (twice per year) or no till, organic amendments and green manure application or permanent ground cover compared to conventional tillage (four times per year). This practice has strong potential to restore soil quality of soils in Mediterranean dryland woody agroecosystems, thereby enhancing their resilience to climate change and long term sustainability.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Regenerative agriculture
 - 2 Cover crops in permanent crops
 - 3 Organic fertilization
 - 4 Reduced till
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

16 - Cover crops in permanent crops

Other one (if any)

46 - No till

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP20 - Spain (CSIC-IRNASA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Regenerative agriculture (RA) in Mediterranean dryland woody agroecosystems include the combination of different sustainable management practices such as reduced tillage or no till, organic amendments and green manure or natural cover (Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2021; Luján Soto et al., 2020, 2021).

This practice has as purposes to restore degraded woody agroecosystems, soil quality and crop performance in rainfed almond orchards in the south of Spain. Reduced tillage with green manure improved physical soil properties (protection of soil against erosion). Reduced tillage with addition of organic amendments improved chemical and biological soil properties (increase of soil organic matter content). Reduced tillage with green manure and organic amendments showed better overall soil quality than each individual practice alone. No tillage with permanent natural covers and organic amendments presented the greatest soil quality improvements compared to conventional management. It was observed that RA combining ground covers and organic amendments presented higher soil quality restoration results and were adopted for longer periods (Luján Soto et al., 2020, 2021).

Major activities / inputs needed to establish/maintain the practice are the combination of different RA practices such as reduced tillage and no tillage with green manure (legume or legume-cereal mixture of common vetch (*Vicia sativa*), bitter vetch (*Vicia ervilia*), and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*)) or natural covers (permanent ground covers of spontaneous vegetation and seeded green manure, managed by grazing with sheep, mowing, chisel plowing, or by a

combination of them), and organic amendments (sheep manure, compost type bokashi, compost made from different organic residues, and organic fertilizers in pellet form), which can be effective for soil quality restoration (Luján Soto et al., 2020, 2021).

The benefits / impacts of these RA include improvement of soil physical properties, soil fertility and soil structure, enhancement of water availability and total and labile soil organic carbon stocks, reduction of soil loss and erosion, increment of aggregate stability, soil nutrient conservation and biological activities. RA as a sustainable farming approach can restore soil quality in degraded dryland agroecosystems, maintaining the nutritional status of tree crops, while combinations of multiple practices were more effective than individual RA practices (Luján Soto et al., 2020, 2021).

Innovator farmers are interested in this regenerative agricultural practice because the establishment of climate resilient agriculture in their almond farms. However, some farmers are reluctant to implement RA, especially if no tillage is promoted, reliable information on crop yield and integrated cost-benefit analyses of RA are required to support large-scale adoption of this practice (Luján Soto et al., 2020, 2021).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Low mean annual precipitation (300 mm) concentrated in few torrential events can limit the application of this practice in semiarid Mediterranean zones characterized by long periods of drought.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Uncertain
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil moisture content can limit the application of this practice during the dry season. Given the water scarcity of the Mediterranean south zone, plant species with shallow root systems and low water requirements are desirable.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No

2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA

Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

Raquel Luján Soto, María Martínez-Mena, Mamen Cuéllar Padilla, Joris de Vente, 2021. Restoring soil quality of woody agroecosystems in Mediterranean drylands through regenerative agriculture. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 306: 107191, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.107191>

Raquel Luján Soto, Mamen Cuéllar Padilla, Joris de Vente, 2020. Participatory selection of soil quality indicators for monitoring the impacts of regenerative agriculture on ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services*, 45: 101157, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101157>

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

Raquel Luján Soto, María Martínez-Mena, Mamen Cuéllar Padilla, Joris de Vente, 2021. Restoring soil quality of woody agroecosystems in Mediterranean drylands through regenerative agriculture. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 306: 107191, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.107191>

Raquel Luján Soto, Mamen Cuéllar Padilla, Joris de Vente, 2020. Participatory selection of soil quality indicators for monitoring the impacts of regenerative agriculture on ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services*, 45: 101157, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101157>

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
-

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.27 - Use of pulp mill and paper mill by-products as soil amendments

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Applying organic sludge from pulp and paper industry to soil for the purpose of improving soil structure and quality as well as decreasing erosion and losses of phosphorus bound to soil.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 fiber sludge (=zero fibres)
 - 2 composted pulp mill sludge (=composted fibres)
 - 3 lime-stabilized pulp mill sludge (lime-stabilized fibres)
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

Other one (if any)

2 - Organic Farming

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P9 - Finland (LUKE)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Sludge from the process water of treatment plant at the pulp and paper mill is either composted or lime-stabilized before its application in agricultural fields. While fiber sludge (zero fiber) consists of cellulose fibers that are too short for the final product of the mill. The main difference between the materials is that nutrient fiber (e.g. composted or lime-stabilized pulp mill sludge) contains phosphorus (P), and nitrogen (N), whereas fiber sludge is a nutrient-poor cellulose material. Despite the name of sludge, the composition of the sludge is not sludge-like, instead the dry matter content is 30–40%.

Mostly after harvest in autumn, pulp mill sludge (20–50 Mg / ha wet weight) is spread evenly on the soil surface by machines used for dry manure application. Thereafter, the soil is tilled to about 10 cm depth during following 24 hours. Crop sowing is not recommended during the following two weeks after application of sludge since microbes bind nitrogen as they decompose the soil tilled fiber.

Before application the water management of the field should be in a good condition. The sludge can be used in all types of fields, but the greatest benefit is likely in low-organic mineral soils. Composted pulp mill sludge is also suitable for organic farming.

Pulp mill sludge can be used to reduce erosion and losses of total P and solid-bound P. In the rainfall simulation study of Rasa et al. (2020), the sludge reduced suspended solids, and total P in percolation water from 40 cm deep monoliths by 60–80% and 40–50%, respectively.

The addition of organic matter improves the living conditions of soil microbes and earthworms increasing the pools of microbial-bound C and N in soil. As the pulp mill sludge is broken

down, microbes secrete adhesives that improve the resistance of crumbs having a positive effect on the soil structure. With the application rate of 40 Mg / ha sludge, 6–7 Mg / ha carbon is added to a field. Due to the high C/nutrient ratios, these soil amendments can be used in much higher quantities than many organic materials that are more nutrient rich, such as manures and composted biosolids (Rasa et al. 2020). At these amounts used the effect on increase of C and N in soil is small which is difficult to detect (Soilfood 2021). If necessary, the treatment can be renewed after a few years.

The organic soil amendments tested by Rasa et al. (2020) had minor effects on cereal yield and grain quality. In the first year after application, the spring cereal yield was about 14% lower in the nutrient-poor fiber sludge treatment compared with the control (no application). This was likely due to immobilization of soil N.

Cadmium concentrations in side streams from pulp and paper industry vary among individual mills. Cadmium may not accumulate in the soil more than 1.5 g / ha per year, for a total 7.5 g / ha over a five-year period (Rasa et al. 2020).

For instance, in Finland, various products (composted pulp mill sludge, lime-stabilized pulp mill sludge and fiber sludge) were applied to approximately 1 400 ha in 2020. The products would be annually sufficient for 30 000-60 000 ha in arable farming with an application rate of 20-40 Mg / ha (Soilfood 2021).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

That is a good practice in Boreal and Nemoral environmental zones. More research is needed on its applicability in other environmental zones.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : The pulp mill sludge can be used in all types of fields, but the greatest benefit is likely in low-organic mineral soils. Erosion is not usually significant in coarse mineral soils, and organic soils already contain a large amount of organic matter.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil must not be too wet during application to avoid compaction. Applying large amounts on steep slopes may be challenging.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain

2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect

Avoid contamination	Adverse Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The use of sludge in agro-forestry areas depends on whether it can be applied and tilled in the topsoil layer of 10 cm.

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

Industrial side streams may contain heavy metals or other harmful elements that may accumulate in the soil and end up in plants (Rasa et al. 2020). High cadmium concentrations in pulp and paper mill sludge may cause problems and therefore its concentration must be monitored sludge products.

Impacts

There is little information how the application of paper mill sludge affects on the crop yield. In the research of Rasa et al. (2020) the effect of nutrient rich fiber (e.g. composted or lime-stabilized pulp mill sludge) on spring cereal was small. Crop sowing, however, is not recommended during the following two weeks after sludge application. In the case of fiber sludge (low nutrient content) the yield was decreased in the first year since microbes bound nitrogen in decomposing the sludge. The use of fiber sludge is recommended when the grass vegetation is stopped and the nitrogen leaching is desired to reduce from the terminated grass field.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)**Documentation**

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.29 - Improved nitrogen fertilization with precision farming based on sensor and satellite technologies

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Development of plants is determined based on the Leaf Area Index, which is measured with sensors and/or satellites. This information is used for variable rate nitrogen fertilization.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	variable rate nitrogen fertilization based on remote sensing
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes

Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

35 - Variable rate fertilizer application

Other one (if any)

41 - Controlled traffic farming

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP6 - Austria (AGES)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	few farmers (“innovators”)

Specificities or further description of the practice

The purpose of this practice is to make the application of nitrogen fertilizer on fields more efficient. Based on data from satellites, drones or hand-held sensors the Leaf Area Index (LAI) can be calculated. With the LAI, potential crop productivity can be estimated and nitrogen fertilization can be optimized. Some handheld devices with sensors use the specific greenness to determine the nitrogen supply of plants. Information on nitrogen requirements can either be used immediately or productivity maps can be created with data for several years and local climate information. Farmers can determine the upper and lower limits of nitrogen application. Further, they can decide if they want to provide more where biomass is less, or less where biomass is less.

Data can be downloaded and then transferred to the tractor terminal directly for variable rate-fertilization, if GPS and an appropriate fertilizer spreader are available. Another option is to load maps on to a mobile device and apply more or less fertilizer manually while driving across the field.

To establish and maintain this practice it is necessary to have reliable data for the creation of productivity maps showing current plant development and modelled productivity. Programs and maps have to be user friendly and available at a reasonable price to be accepted by farmers.

If applied correctly, this practice can be used to minimize N leaching. Especially in vulnerable zones, if the strategy of providing less where biomass is less is adopted. If the strategy of

applying more where biomass is less is chosen, the practice can improve yields and profitability. As the production of N fertilizer needs a lot of energy it is important to use it more efficiently. Optimal nitrogen fertilization is also known to prevent some plant diseases.

Economic benefits for farmers through lower costs for fertilizer on the one hand, and improved yields and product quality on the other hand can be achieved with this practice. Especially when using maps based on satellite or sensor data, that are available online, the amount of work for farmers is reasonable. The practice can also be applied on smaller farms. With the data currently available it is possible to use the system on fields smaller than 1 ha. One factor that could keep farmers from adopting the practice is the initial investment into machinery, for fully automatic variable rate fertilization.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	No
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

Spiegel, H., Sandén, T., Essl, L., & Vuolo, F. (2021). Toward Improved Nitrogen Fertilization with Precision Farming Based on Sensor and Satellite Technologies. In *Women in Precision Agriculture* (pp. 69-83). Springer, Cham.

Argento, F., Anken, T., Abt, F., Vogelsanger, E., Walter, A., & Liebisch, F. (2021). Site-specific nitrogen management in winter wheat supported by low-altitude remote sensing and soil data. *Precision Agriculture*, 22(2), 364-386.

Other general comments

Spiegel, H., Sandén, T., Essl, L., & Vuolo, F. (2021). Toward Improved Nitrogen Fertilization with Precision Farming Based on Sensor and Satellite Technologies. In *Women in Precision Agriculture* (pp. 69-83). Springer, Cham.

Argento, F., Anken, T., Abt, F., Vogelsanger, E., Walter, A., & Liebisch, F. (2021). Site-specific nitrogen management in winter wheat supported by low-altitude remote sensing and soil data. *Precision Agriculture*, 22(2), 364-386.

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.31 - Rotavation of grassland before ploughing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Rotavation of grass or grass/clover before ploughing to promote turnover of organic matter and reduce risk of N₂O leaching

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

21 - Grassland with legumes

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P7 - Denmark (AU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Rotavation of grass or grass/clover before ploughing is widely recommended to farmers in Denmark to enhance decomposition of the turf. Rotavation is an intense, shallow tillage that leaves residues closer to the soil surface, therefore warming up faster. Also, more oxygen will be available for decomposition. Ploughing typically takes place around 2 weeks after the rotavation. A better soil-residue contact can affect N mineralization, nitrification and denitrification, and hence N₂O emissions, but whether this is an increase (Kong et al., 2018) or decrease (unpublished results) will depend on soil nitrate availability and wetness.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

not so relevant in hot and dry climates

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	No
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Not known

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	NA
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

Risk of erosion is a serious concern on sloping land. Timing of N release and risk of N leaching is another concern.

Soil challenges

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Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.33 - Bio-subsoiling

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Bio-subsoiling is defined as a compaction mitigation practice that implies the use of deep-rooted cover crops or main crops as a biotic mechanism for creating functional bio-pores (root channels) and aggregation in compacted subsoil layers

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected

Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

18 - Deep rootening plants

Other one (if any)

15 - Cover crops

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P7 - Denmark (AU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The bio-subsoiling is a biological method that involves the growth of deep-rooted crops. The plant species used for bio-subsoiling are typically cover crops or perennial crops. Depending on the species selected, the potential to mitigate subsoil compaction differs between monocotyledons (fibrous-rooted) and dicotyledons (tap-rooted). Their potential as bio-subsoilers may also be affected by length of growing period, degree of compactness, soil type, climate, and plant age, among others.

The bio-subsoiling is a biotic mechanism for soil compaction mitigation. The bio-subsoiling aims for the use of plants with roots that penetrate compacted soil layers and create fissures, bio-pores and promote aggregation that can improve pore system functionality by recovering the pore connectivity and increasing the pore number and pore diameter, as well as the water and gas transport through them. Additionally, the created bio-pores can be reused by subsequent crop roots, which allows roots to explore the compacted layer for nutrients and water.

The successful improvement of soil pore functionality by the practice of a compacted subsoil requires time for root development, with perennial species having better root development with time. The use of mixture may improve the root architecture, and hence pore architecture, in the compacted layers. The choice of plant species to be used as bio-subsoilers might imply changes in the cropping system.

Farmers might be interested in the recovery of soil functionality that directly could increase crop yield, as well as the environmental benefit implied. However, the time dependent of the practice may be a matter of concern by farmers.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	NA
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

No data

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

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Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.34 - Lightweight autonomous field robot

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The lightweight autonomous field robots are agricultural vehicles capable of doing field operations by working in fleets within a field.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

41 - Controlled traffic farming

Other one (if any)

9 - Integrated pest management

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P7 - Denmark (AU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The main characteristic of the practice is the use of lightweight autonomous vehicles (LAV) in the fields instead of traditional machinery.

The main purpose is to reduce or replace the use of heavy machinery in certain operations that do not require high power, automatize them and acquire data for other purposes such as decision making (for instance, image analysis to assess the proportion of insects in a field, amount of weeds, or clover/grass ratio).

Because it is in an early stage of development, the main inputs needed to establish and maintain the practice are first, to increase the farmer awareness regarding the availability of this tool and its possible benefits. And second, to conduct more studies to address and quantify if the potential benefits of using LAV can compete with traditional technologies.

The primary benefits of this practice are that using LAV instead of heavy machinery could reduce the potential risk of soil compaction to some extent in temperate regions. At this stage, traditional machines are still needed but the combination of both could reduce the number wheel passes that can cause compaction during the operations. In addition, these vehicles are equipped with powerful sensors and technologies that can be used for precision agriculture tasks like applying fertilizer in selected spots or precise spraying of weeds. However, because LAVs have limited capacity, they are expected to work in fleets which could increase traffic

and imply longer working times. This practice could also have socioeconomical impacts since one person could potentially manage a fleet of LAVs, hence, requiring less human resources.

The use of LAVs in Denmark is starting to become more popular thanks to the marketing campaigns, workshops, and collaboration with universities. Farmers like the simplicity of the robot as it was designed to be easily fixed and with the same kind of mechanical parts as a traditional tractor. However, it is still unknown whether or not farmers are willing to embrace this new technology, mainly due to the lack of examples of successful applications and quantifiable benefits.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	NA
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	NA
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

/

Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.35 - Rotovated band seeding

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A tillage system for row crops which reduces cultivation and tillage with a rotary tiller to the stripes, in which the seeds are planted. Between the tilled strips, the soil and soil cover remain untilled.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	rotary band seeding
2	
3	
4	
5	

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	NA
Organic matter and nutrient management	NA
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	NA
Water Management	NA

Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

50 - Strip tillage

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P24 - Switzerland (AGS)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Not relevant
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	early adopters
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

A strip rotor, often combined with a cultivator for primary tillage, is used to prepare the seedbed for strip seeding. Typically, the working depth of the rotor is 10-15cm, and the cultivator loosens the soil to a maximum of 25cm. The plants are seeded into the tilled soil strips that cover up to 50% of the total surface at most. Between the tilled strips the soil and the soil cover remains untouched. Optionally, a herbicide can be applied to kill-off the vegetation in the untilled strips. Alternatively, mechanical operations can control the vegetation between the tilled strips. In regions with elevated precipitation this practice is used to cultivate e.g. maize into a growing meadow.

The practice combines the benefits of untilled, stable soils between the tilled strips and the benefits of a tilled seedbed for plant growth in the tilled strips. The fine seedbed increases mineralisation and allows swift drying and warming of the soil in spring. Furthermore, the rotor allows the incorporation of manure or slurry.

The practice is applicable to arable crops grown in rows, such as maize, rapeseed, sugar beet, sunflower or soya. In Switzerland, the practice is especially widespread for maize-sowing, especially after (or even in, see above) a multi-year grassland.

The two steps of seedbed preparation and seeding can be combined into one field operation. However, the combination is only recommended when the soil is dry and warm, e.g. for autumn-sown crops such as rapeseed. If the operations are done separately, GNSS*-assisted steering facilitates the match of seeding machine and tilled soil strips.

For instance, in Switzerland, the field operations are usually executed by contractors due to the relatively high machine costs and the needed level of proficiency.

*GNSS = Global Navigation Satellite System, such as GPS, GLONASS, Galileo or BeiDou

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Adverse Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The application of this practice in organic farming is limited due to the challenging herbicide-free control of the vegetation between the tilled strips (BioAktuell, 2014).

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

According to Agridea (2010, 2019) the practice enhances the soils structure and stability between the tilled rows. Additionally, the nutrient losses the sources claim that nutrient-leaching is reduced. Prasuhn (2020) documented reduced erosion in the Frienisberg Region (Switzerland) due to the widespread application of this and other soil management practices.

Impacts

Agridea (2010) states, that yields are comparable to conventional tillage practices. The practice may cause higher pressure of weeds, especially root-propagating species and grasses, and snails (Agridea, 2019). Swiss farmers can apply for targeted direct payments of 200 CHF / ha if they respect certain conditions linked to the application of this practice.

Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.36 - Humus Balance Calculator

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The soil organic matter (SOM) content of a soil is of central importance for soil fertility and is strongly dependent on soil management. Humus balance calculators allow farmers to estimate whether the SOM content of a particular field is likely to increase, remain stable or decrease.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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1
2
3
4
5
—

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	NA
Water Management	NA

Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	Decision support tool

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

No data

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P24 - Switzerland (AGS)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Humus balance calculators are simple tools to assess whether the SOM management of arable soils is in balance or not. For this purpose so called ‘humus balances’ of arable fields are calculated for a specific year. Multiple ‘humus balance tools exist (Brock et al., 2013), in the following description we focus on a tool developed in Switzerland.

For instance, the Agrosopes humus balance calculator is based on the method of Neyroud et al. (1997), which allows to calculate the balances with relatively few management data. The method has been improved and validated with data from long-term experiments (Oberholzer et al., 2012). Furthermore, the tool allows farmers to assess which measures, if any, can contribute to which degree to an improvement. Agrosopes humus balance calculator is available free of charge at www.humusbilanz.ch or www.bilan-humique.ch. It contains instructions for use as well as information on how to interpret the results and advise on how to adjust the soil management. In the basic version, the user needs to provide information on the clay content and the pH of the soil, details about the main and cover crops as well as about organic amendments. An expert version allows to provide and process some additional data, such as yield and harvesting date of the main crop. The farm and management data entered can be stored and used repeatedly or supplemented annually. Currently, the humus balance calculator is available in German and French. From 2017 to 2022 the tool is used by farmers in a regional

policy program. It is expected, that this test application by more than 200 farmers will lead to improvements of the tool.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : The current humus balance calculator of Agroscope is not suitable to assess organic soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No

2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	No Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	No Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The current version of Agroscope's humus balance calculator is parametrized according and applicable to typical Swiss arable farming systems.

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.38 - Biofumigation against plant-pathogens

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Biofumigation by using naturally produced plant compounds to manage plant-parasitic nematodes. Fresh glucosinolate-rich (GSLs) Brassicaceae crops are chopped and incorporated into the soil that releases highly toxic volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Cellular disruption and enzymatic hydrolysis of GSL release degradation products, specifically isothiocyanates (ITCs) capable of killing or antagonizing plant-parasitic nematodes. This practice also reduces infections by the cephalosporium fungus and weed competition, incorporates organic material in the soil that is advantageous for soil structure and for the availability of nutrients.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

8 - Biofumigation

Other one (if any)

9 - Integrated pest management

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P19 - Portugal (INIAV)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected

Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected
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Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The biofumigation practice against corn-parasitic nematodes described here is being used by a farmer in MDN in PT (Quinta da Choldra). This exploitation has precision agriculture farming of maize irrigated with center-pivot. In this field, root-knot nematodes and the cephalosporium fungus were reducing the maize yield. To avoid the use of chemical pesticides, this farmer chose to use Raphanus, a biofumigation crop from the Brassicaceae family, associated with black oat and barley to cover the soil after maize was harvested (winter time Nov-Mar) and to incorporate in the soil before maize seeding (Mar). The innovation is related to the fact that is scarcely used in our country. In this precision agriculture farming exploitation it is applied to aim at reducing root-knot nematodes and prevent wounds in the roots of young corn and reducing infections by the cephalosporium fungus. It is an efficient technique but becomes very expensive and unnecessary in areas without the presence of phytopathogens. This farmer seeded the biofumigation crop mixture only in areas affected by the pests with a significant reduction in production to reduce costs and to recover more easily the investment made. This crop mixture has small seeds and a special seeding machine is needed, which represents an extra cost (in this case a machine was rented). What is worthy of mentioning is that this farmer made informative videos available online (links are provided below) with the costs of application of this practice: Raphanus and black oat seeds 11Kg/ha with 5€/Kg cost; the service of seeding

costs 50€/ha; consumption and emissions of 15L of diesel equivalent to 45Kg CO₂. The time of incorporation of the biofumigation crop in the soil has to be carefully managed since it has to be incorporated green to take advantage of the biofumigation effect and at the Brassica flowering stage. This practice is used in PT in the rainy season, it might be needed to wait until it is possible for the machines to incorporate the green biomass into the soil using a shredder and then a harrowing followed by a roller. The crop should be shredded as finely as possible before soil incorporation for efficacy. The efficiency depends mainly on the following factors: the Brassica species used, which determines the type of isothiocyanates (ITCs) released; the cultivar used that will determine both the glucosinolate-rich (GSLs) concentration in tissues and the total biomass produced, and hence the potential amount of GLS buried in the soil; and the timing of the destruction of the fumigant crop. To maximize biofumigation, it should be destroyed at the beginning of the flowering stage when biomass and GLS contents in plants reach their maximum values (Kirkegaard and Sarwar 1998; Sarwar and Kirkegaard 1998). One disadvantage is that after more than two decades of studies on biofumigation, the method is not widely used. Probably due to the reported efficacy still is lower than the chemical products. One of the greatest advantages is environmental since it reduces contamination by avoiding the use of nematicides and fungicides. It covers the soil in the rainy season that prevents soil compaction at the surface and helps in improving soil structure, and reduces weeds. There are no reports on negative impacts on beneficial microorganisms associated with this method and it is not host-specific (ITCs can inhibit a series of soil-borne diseases). Brassicas' can be used as green manure crops and they grow faster (appreciated by farmers).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Rainfall or irrigation is needed at the time of plant incorporation in the soil, to ensure effective hydrolysis of GSLs (Morra and Kirkegaard, 2002), as well as efficient breakdown of plant tissues. The biofumigant potential of a crop relies on: achieving as much biomass as possible and crop access to long day lengths and high ultraviolet (UV) radiation, which is important for the production of the precursors to the toxic volatiles released on soil incorporation.

Depending of the environmental zone, autumn-established biofumigants for overwintering have lower potential than summer biofumigant crops. Examples of crops: Indian mustard is a summer crop (needs high UV radiation) with growing period of 8–14 weeks; oil radish is a winter crop and incorporation occurs in spring.

2 week gap between incorporating a biofumigant and planting a new crop. This is to avoid phytotoxic effects in the new crop from biofumigant organic matter breakdown.

warm soils ($>10^{\circ}\text{C}$) – for incorporation of biofumigant material, which helps toxic gases move through the soil. Low soil temperatures limit efficacy.

Climatic limitations will also be dependent on the plant pests or pathogens to be targeted. They have different thermal limits and optimal temperature requirements depending on their species.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping ($<2\%$)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep ($>60\%$)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : It is a practice suited for peatlands/organic soils. Peats are a natural habitat for nematodes and it is normal to find phytoparasitic nematodes in them. To choose the biofumigation crop it is necessary to have good knowledge of the soil pH, moisture content, and plant pathogens. By using this practice less chemical pesticides are used. On the other hand, there is the need to incorporate the biofumigation crop green biomass into the soil by using a shredder and then a harrowing followed by a roller.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

if soils < 50% of field capacity: summer crops may need irrigation prior to maceration and incorporation.

75% < Soil moisture < 100%: moist, but not sodden. The right soil moisture content is so critical that irrigation should be considered if the equipment is available rather than waste the crop by destroying it in the wrong conditions.

Soil temperature 10°C: to maximise volatile gas dispersion through the soil after incorporation.

The ideal timing for maceration and incorporation of summer biofumigants is when the crop is at early to mid-flowering when the foliage is still succulent.

Isothiocyanates are highly toxic volatile compounds and their effectiveness depends on many factors including pH, temperature and soil moisture. In volatile toxicity assays, isothiocyanates were more toxic at higher temperatures compared to lower temperatures (5–20 °C tested, in vitro and with soil (moisture content 75% of field capacity); sand (pH 7.2, 3.26% OM), loam (pH 4.9, 6.77% OM), and peat (pH 5.69, 31.55% OM) (Matthiessen et al., 2005)

Soil texture: lighter-textured soils with low OM content are better suited (Kirkegaard, 2009), since isothiocyanates get fixed to OM by sorption, and are therefore less active against soil-borne pathogens and nematodes. Lower OM content occurs less sorption of the isothiocyanates.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain

2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect

Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(02\)00153-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(02)00153-0)

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

There are economic factors influencing the grower's perception of how to manage the plant-parasitic nematode pests, such as the high cost of the biofumigation practices relative to other management options, the price of the commodity per hectare, and the value of the crop in the agricultural market. In the case of a less-value crop such as maize the cost of this practice cannot be affordable. One way of reducing costs is to apply the practice specifically where the damages to the crop by the plant-parasitic nematodes occur. A very precise knowledge of the farm is needed, so in precision agriculture farming is more practicable. Considering these economic constraints, we classified as uncertain the potential application of this practice in the farming systems extensive small-scale, extensive farming in less favoured areas, agro-forestry (agrisilvicultural), and agro-forestry (silvopastoral).

Limiting soil factors

- <https://www.fas.scot/downloads/technical-note-tn735-biofumigation-to-suppress-pests-weeds-and-diseases/>
- Matthiessen, J.N.; Shackleton, M.A. Biofumigation: Environmental impacts on the biological activity of diverse pure and plant-derived isothiocyanates. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 2005, 61, 1043–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1086>

Soil challenges

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Impacts

/

Other general comments

<https://www.quintadacholda.pt/>

<https://milhoamarelo.pt/2021/01/05/bio-fumigacao-cultura-de-cobertura-de-precisao-cap-1-2/>

<https://www.agroportal.pt/cultura-de-cobertura-para-a-biofumigacao-gestao-da-biomassa-2-3/>

<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004364713152>

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/42948308>

<https://doi.org/10.1071/A98124>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r1xcq233Vj8>

<https://www.best4soil.eu/assets/factsheets/11.pdf>

<https://www.best4soil.eu/database>

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.39 - Associated rapeseed

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

This practice is a specification/example of 'intercropping'. It's the fact to associate winter rapeseed with companion plants (generally frost-sensitive legumes) that are not harvested but just serves the rapeseed. The legumes tested were : Alexandria clover, lentils, faba beans, dwarf white clover.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	NA
Crop protection	Yes

Water Management	NA
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

22 - Intercropping

Other one (if any)

23 - Legume integration

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P5 - Belgium (Wallonia) (CRAW)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	early adopters
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Concretely, we sow rapeseed and companion plants simultaneously. They will develop in association during the autumn and then the legumes will freeze. And the rape will start and take advantage of the after-effects in terms of nitrogen. The advantages are that the legumes will compete with the weeds, so there is little or no need for weed control. Moreover, there are less insect attacks, because they are disturbed thanks to the legumes.

We can also sow rapeseed with white clover, or alfalfa, or birdsfoot trefoil. These are also leguminous plants but they are not frost-sensitive so when we harvest the rapeseed the following year, they will still be there. The advantage of this variation is that we will have an intermediate cover crop already in place that will protect the soil, compete with weeds, and store nitrogen in the soil after the harvest. Thus, After harvest a cereal crop can be sown directly in the cover crop, because the cover crop provides an adequate soil structure.

Technical specifications:

Does not require very specific equipment. Just knowledge of the plants, and some adaptations to the technical itinerary.

It is necessary to sow as early as possible (leguminous plants need temperature), normally we sow rapeseed around September 15th, but with this practice we do it on August 15th. So it requires an adaptation: we need rapeseed varieties that are more resistant to elongation, for example. It is also necessary to adapt the weeding, as it is a technique adapted to organic farming. Moreover, it needs a previous crop that is already harvested on August 15th, so the crop rotation only provides limited options.

Points of attention :

In terms of weed control: be careful with the active substances used because if you use classic products you can also destroy the legumes.

Secondly, it is necessary to adapt the fertilization. It is useless to fertilize as much as in classic rapeseed cultivation because the leguminous plants already fertilize for a certain amount the rapeseed in nitrogen.

Thirdly, there are unsuitable plants, for example the vesse in Belgium. Because it is not freeze-dried, it will rise in the crop after winter, and at harvest it will cause problems. Or also non-leguminous plants, we will not associate rapeseed with phacelia or oats for example. Because they will compete with rapeseed.

Popularity:

What farmers generally like about this practice is the fact that there is less phyto treatment. Also the fact that there is a gain regarding the rotation: there are after effects at the level of general fertility of the soil, we have soils in better condition (richer, better structured). On the one hand, because rapeseed itself is a crop where the soil is not worked very much and there are a lot of residues, which allows to really restore a degraded soil. On the other hand because the benefits brought by the companion plant reinforces this regenerative effect of the rapeseed crop.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Drought is limiting because then the legumes won't grow and thus do not play their role in colza protection and nutrition.

Also if there is no frost in the winter: because then if we use spring feldspar as a companion plant for example, and we sow it in the fall, it will grow back with the rapeseed in the next spring because it will not have been killed by the frost. This will typically be a problem for harvesting if the buckwheat is not mature at the same time as the rapeseed, but also a problem for sorting between the two plants after harvest.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : Theoretically, yes, but the practice will be all the more relevant if the soil has lower carbon organic content (poor).

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil has to be not too rich in nitrogen, and has to have sulfur.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect

Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

We may note that drought is not that specific as a limiting factor to this practice, it is limiting in general.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

Permanently irrigated land / rice fields : Theoretically yes, but farmers don't do it with rapeseed because it's not profitable enough.

Terrace Farming / Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming : You can't grow rapeseed without mechanization.

Limiting soil factors

Sulfur tough can always be brought in the form of fertilizer.

Soil challenges

Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils / Avoid contamination : Because it reduces mineral fertilization.

Optimal soil structure / Enhance soil biodiversity: Because there are more roots, also because we have a diversity of plants so we favor more microorganisms.

Enhance soil nutrient use efficiency : We see positive after-effects on the scale of the rotation, in the following cultures we gain yield because we have enriched the soil the year before.

Impacts

Impacts on crop yield: On average, we gain between 0 and 5% in yield. But the extreme values of yield measured range from -10 to +20%. The poorer the soil, the higher the yield and vice versa.

Impacts on farm profitability: Little impact at the global level. Beneficial or neutral. Neutral because in general the savings made by avoiding the use of herbicides and fertilizers compensate for the cost of additional seeds for companion plants. Beneficial because, in the rotation, at the time of the rapeseed year the benefit is only slightly positive (a few tens of euros per

hectare) but at the scale of the rotation there is a little more benefit because money is earned on the following crops with the yield gained thanks to the beneficial effects on the soil of the associated rapeseed.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.40 - Tyre Inflation System (TIS)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Tyre Inflation System is a system which allows the adaptation of the inflation pressure of the tires in order to improve their performance according to the type of surface. In field, the reduction in pressure increases the footprint on the soil, which has the effect of increasing performance in terms of traction while reducing soil compaction. On the road, increasing the pressure especially reduces tire wear and fuel consumption.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Central Tyre Inflation System (CTIS)
 - 2 Tyre Pressure Adjustment System (TPAS)
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes

Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

44 - Low pressure in tires

Other one (if any)

37 - Models for soil compaction risk assessment

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P1 - France (INRAE)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Yes
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Yes
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	early adopters
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	early adopters
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Unknown
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Unknown
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	few farmers (“innovators”)

Specificities or further description of the practice

What are the main characteristics/elements of the practice (including technical specifications)?

A central tyre pressure control system is a system added or initially integrated into a tractor which allows the tire inflation pressure to be adjusted according to the traffic conditions of the tractor.

What are the purposes/functions of the practice?

In the field, low pressures are needed to spread the weight of the machine and to maximise grip. Conversely, on the road higher pressures are needed to give stability, fuel efficiency and minimise tyre wear.

What major activities/inputs are needed to establish/ maintain the practice?

It is necessary to have a compressor which can inflate the tires fairly quickly.

What are the benefits/impacts of the practice?

Resellers of central tire inflation system promise reduce fuel consumption by up to 15%, tyre wear by up to 20%, and reduced soil compaction increases yield by up to 6%.

A central tyre pressure control system should to allow save fuel, minimise soil compaction and reduce tyre wear by allowing maintaining the correct tyre pressures for varying load, field and speed conditions.

The appropriate tyre pressure is usually estimated by the farmer himself using the tyre pressure table. Additionally the farmer uses his own expertise and experience to optimise the pressure. But it is possible to use, for example AgroPressure by Michelin, to automat pressure adjustment, with calculation of the right tyre pressure based on machine use, soil conditions and equipment specifics, and simulate different scenarios regarding risk on compaction (with Terranimo, model for prediction of the risk of soil compaction due to agricultural field traffic).

What do farmers like/dislike about the practice?

Farmers like this system but it is too expensive.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The drier the climate, the less interest there is in this system, since it is in wet periods that soils are most sensitive to compaction

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No limit has been identified. The system is all the more interesting as the soil texture is sensitive to compaction.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes

2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	NA
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil biodiversity	NA
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	NA
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The practice is interesting to use whenever there are soils sensitive to compaction.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

The practice has the same benefits as any practice aimed at reducing soil compaction, for which the consequences are not necessarily identical (e.g., Nawaz et al., 2013).

Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

Nawaz M, Bourrié G, Trolard F, Soil compaction impact and modelling. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, Springer Verlag/EDP Sciences/INRA, 2013, 33 (2), pp.291-309, <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01201344>

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.41 - Associated beets

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Association of sugar beet with faba bean to attract crop protection agents and fight aphids more effectively. Possibility of association in full or in strips (strips of beet and alternating beet).

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	NA
Tillage and traffic	NA
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	NA

Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

9 - Integrated pest management

Other one (if any)

1 - Conservation Agriculture

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P5 - Belgium (Wallonia) (CRAW)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Beetroot replaces insecticides to fight the beet yellows virus.

To compensate for the ban on neonicotinoids, Greenotec has set up trials on the associated beet crop to control aphids, vectors of the beet yellows virus. The association with faba bean seems to have a positive impact on the presence of beneficials and thus reduce the number of aphids.

Sowing 8-10 feet of faba beans before sowing the beet. Lighten the herbicide program so as not to kill the bean. The bean will attract pollinating beneficials, which will lay their eggs on the beets and naturally control the aphids.

Possibility to reduce/remove the use of insecticides in beets.

Additional seed cost, more precise weed control and possibility of failure if weed flora is too strong + loss of yield if bean density is too high.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

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Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

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Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	NA
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Beneficial Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

Less use of pesticides

Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.42 - Regenerative viticulture using spent mushroom substrate (SMS)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The main Objective of this practice is to improve the quality of grapes from improving the quality of vineyard soils. Vineyard soils are unbalanced and not fertile and a new methodology or regenerative agriculture technique is proposed based on the use of SMS to increase the organic matter (OM) content of soils. The OM improves water and nutrient retention ability and increase soil aggregation enhancing the regeneration of vineyard soils and increasing the quality of grapes.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

16 - Cover crops in permanent crops

Other one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP20 - Spain (CSIC-IRNASA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

An introduction or background to the innovative practice here described and the results obtained in general are included below.

Individual application of organic amendments such as biochar, compost from olive wastes, sheep manure or from biowaste and green waste (Sánchez-Monedero et al., 2019), agro-food-derived composts elaborated mainly using exhausted grape marc and wastes from citrus juice production or cattle manure (Rubio et al., 2013) or Grape prunings combined with sheep manure (Pereg et al., 2018), or green covers such as leguminous covers (Pereg et al., 2018), permanent cover consisting of *Brachypodium distachyon* or covers of barley, rye and spontaneous vegetation (Capo-Bauçá et al., 2019; Ruiz-Colmenero et al., 2011) have been carried out in vineyards from Spain and other European countries with the aim to reduce mineral fertilizers and agro-chemicals and to improve the health of the soil and the vineyard plants.

Chemical parameters as soil total organic carbon (TOC) and nitrogen content, pH or nutrient cycling and biological parameters, such as soil microbial biomass, soil basal respiration, enzymatic activities, and aggregate stability were evaluated and indicated the crop nutritional status and productivity were improved. Moreover, these tests resulted in reduced soil loss by erosion and the treatments also noted a decrease in the runoff coefficients.

However, the combination of organic amendments and green covers or organic plus inorganic amendments and cover crops, as it is proposed in this practice, is less frequent. In this practice, individual or simultaneous application of an low-cost organic residue, spent mushroom

substrate (SMS), re-composted with ofite mineral power (OF), and plant cover (rye) in vineyard soils of La Rioja region (Spain) was assayed.

This agricultural practice has as aim to regenerate and remineralize the soil by increasing the soil organic matter content and mineral elements and to enhance the microbiological activities of vineyard soils to improve vineyard yield. The specific objectives which could be achieved are:

- a) Identify and fine-tune the most appropriate combination of techniques for the improvement of soils in each case,
- b) Increase the OM of the soil without interfering in the growth processes of the vineyard or in the technological maturation of the grape,
- c) Reduce the erosion of the vineyard and contribute to increasing functional biodiversity,
- d) Improve the carbon footprint balance in vineyards, favouring their sustainability,
- e) Reduce the use of chemical inputs (fertilizers and pesticides) whose manufacture generates a large amount of greenhouse gases (GHGs),
- f) Improve the nutritional balance of the vineyard in problem areas and, consequently, the quality of its grapes,
- g) Achieve greater resistance to diseases on the part of the vine and promote the biological processes of the soil by adding microbiological and mineral products.

Major activities or inputs to establish and maintain this practice are the annual application of SMS, SMS+ofite, and SMS+ofite+cover crop treatments.

The SMS amendment produces a significant increase in the soil organic carbon content. The application of these residues also led to an increase in macro and micronutrients maintained over time. In addition, the effect on the soil biochemical parameters (soil microbial activity, abundance and structure) is also relevant.

The vineyard farmers agree with this practice, although its effect on the vineyard yield has to be evaluated at long-term.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

The Soils of Spain, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-20541-0_2

Soil challenges

VITIREG, Grupo Operativo Viticultura Regenerativa. <http://vitireg.org/>

Impacts

VITIREG, Grupo Operativo Viticultura Regenerativa. <http://vitireg.org/>

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)**Documentation**

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.43 - Regeneration of mine soils by grazing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Mining activity leaves the landscape with no vegetation and very poor soil-forming material for subsequent ecosystem development. The restoration of areas affected is an urgent need being grazing an innovative practice suggested for application in post-mining land.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Green covers
 - 2 Grazing
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected

Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

36 - Land reclamation

Other one (if any)

29 - Cover crop grazing

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP20 - Spain (CSIC-IRNASA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Grazing plays a key role in regulating the structure and function of ecosystems and to rehabilitation mined lands because of the lower land productivity required compared to cropping.

The purpose of this practice is to regenerate the soil by increasing the plant communities and to enhance the microbiological activities of soils.

Initial activities must respond to specific needs of each site on climate, topography or sensitivity for the environment and social demands consistent with the objectives of sustainable development. The rehabilitation programs would include revegetation actions based mainly on the seeding or planting of species with short life forms such as herbs, grasses and shrubs. After the grazing contribution and of the organic matter from the livestock could improve the soil properties and the survival, growth, and nutritional status of plants.

The livestock is a tool to increase the nutrients of the soil. The organic matter provided with their faeces enhances the growth of native species of grasses and other plants. The biosystem is improved by the increase in macro and micronutrients maintained over time.

The farmer agree with this practice on the recovery of soils from abandoned mines because it has positive effects on different goods and services, including erosion control, carbon sequestration in soils and biomass or wood production (Bindang Oná et al., 2021) . However the stocking

intensity is low due to it is necessary to control the mobility of toxic elements in the soil profiles of revegetated tailings and the potential metal transfer to the food chain (Metsaranta et al., 2018). Effects of pollutants on animal welfare has to be controlled as it is indicated in previous comment.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : This practice is not specifically suited for the management of organic soils

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Most of the Inceptisols have high agricultural potential, although when located in the xeric and ustic moisture regimes, they require irrigation. In mountain areas, their exploitation is limited to forestry or livestock. Aridisols constitute the only soil order defined by their aridity degree. These soils have an aridic (torric) soil moisture regime, i.e., they lack water available to plants over extended periods of time. The soil control section has been primarily conditioned by a climatic aridity, which can also influence the profile properties and their position in the relief (thin top soil, high stone content, low moisture retention or excessive runoff).

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	No
Large-scale corporate farming	No

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	NA
Impacts on farm profitability	NA
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Beneficial Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

The Soils of Spain, Springer, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-20541-0_2

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.44 - Rotational grazing in agrosilvopastoral system

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Practice of rotational grazing (with mono- or multi-species like cattle, pigs, sheeps, goats or turkeys) to combat the loss of natural regeneration and soil degradation in degraded agrosilvopastoral areas, such as “Dehesa” in Spain, providing effective ecosystem management systems and improving soil quality.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Regenerative agriculture
 - 2 Regenerative grazing
 - 3 Multispecies rotational grazing
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes

Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

14 - Agroforestry

Other one (if any)

29 - Cover crop grazing

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

LTP20 - Spain (CSIC-IRNASA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Yes
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The premise of this practice is to revitalize multifunctional Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral systems using dynamic and profitable operational practices.

More concretely, holistic grazing and other Regenerative Agricultural techniques (Keyline, inoculations) are being demonstrated in 2 Quercus-based silvopastoral systems in Spain and Italy. Project partners are also working with their network of farmers to implement regenerative agricultural practices on their lands, thereby “replicating” the project’s activities.

LIFE Regenerate’s project main objective is to demonstrate that small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) farms of the Mediterranean silvopastoral systems can become self-sufficient and profitable based on resource efficiency principles and incorporating added value products, both at a demonstration and a larger scale.

LIFE Regenerate has the following specific objectives:

1. Combat the loss of natural regeneration and soil degradation in 100 ha of degraded silvopastoral areas by providing effective, mosaic landscape management procedures and improving soil quality;
2. Recover the practice of multispecies rotational grazing, adapted to improve natural capital and optimize commercial advantages;
3. Recycle biomass waste within the farm, reducing external input of fodder and creating alternative sources of income;

4. Replicate the project's best practices to 5,000 ha in Spain, Italy & Portugal, proving it is a representative, effective model;
5. Integrate new technologies (Adaptive Multi-Paddock (AMP) Grazing system, Mushroom inoculation (truffles), Amendment, Tree planting, Keyline with grass tiller, Direct seeding, reuse of biomass to produce: mushrooms, compost, biochar) and monitoring of project advances;
6. Influence policy-making and involve external stakeholders to promote replication and long-term sustainability.

Specific purposes / functions of this practice include:

- Improvement of soil quality by increasing carbon sink, water retention capacity, soil nutrient availability, beneficial microorganisms, and prevention of erosion;
- Improvement of pasture production and pasture quality (25-50% of agricultural land), leading to self-sufficiency in animal feed and higher profitability of livestock raising practices;
- Increase in plant diversity (15%) and biodiversity overall (20%);
- Improvement of tree health and resilience in 50 ha of woodlands and 2,000 new multispecies trees planted;
- Overall increase in animal health and productivity, through reduction in mortality and decrease in calving intervals.

Major activities / inputs needed to establish/maintain the practice are the existence of a silvopastoral systems such as the Spanish "Dehesa", Portuguese "Montado" and Sardinian "Meriagos" where oak based forest systems and animals are combined. Dehesas typically have a low tree density, around 60 trees/ha; animals live off the pasture that grows beneath the trees, and the acorns that the trees produce. Animals such as cows, pigs, sheep, and turkeys are being managed under this system.

The benefits / impacts of the Regenerative agriculture include:

- Enhancement of soil formation and health, water retention, carbon sequestration, biodiversity above and below soil, stability, ecosystem services and resilience
- Reduction of synthetic fertiliser and pesticide use, GHG emissions, agricultural land required, waste to be managed and treated, soil compaction risk, soil erosion and pollution.

Innovator farmers are interested in this regenerative agricultural practice.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Scarce precipitation in summer season and length of summer drought can limit the application of this practice in the Mediterranean south zone.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	No
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

FINAL_Position Paper_Regenerative Agriculture.pdf (<https://regenerate.eu/en/downloads/downloads-559.html>).

LIFE Regenerate Project, <https://regenerate.eu/en/>

Xabier Díaz de Otálora, Lur Epelde, Josune Arranz, Carlos Garbisu, Roberto Ruiz, Nerea Mandaluniz, 2021. Regenerative rotational grazing management of dairy sheep increases springtime grass production and topsoil carbon storage, *Ecological Indicators*, 125: 107484, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107484>.

EuroSheep project, <https://eurosheep.network/a-simple-approach-to-rotational-grazing/>

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
-

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.45 - low emission slurry spreading

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Low emission slurry spreading is a technique used to increase the amount of nutrient available and reduce the loss of nutrients to air or water. There are several different methods used for this practice each has specific equipment.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 LESS
 - 2 trailing shoe
 - 3 trailing hose
 - 4 shallow injection
 - 5 splash plate
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected

Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	grassland

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

34 - Use of biofertilizers

Other one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P26 - United Kingdom (AFBI)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Low emission slurry spreading (LESS) is a practice which involves alternative or new equipment to apply slurry to grassland. The principal aim of LESS is to reduce ammonia emissions. There are a range of different equipment options available to undertake LESS. In Northern Ireland some of the equipment used include a trailing shoe, trailing hose, shallow injection and an inverted splash plate. Evaluation of these equipment shows that there are significant differences in their effectiveness reduce odour, ammonia emissions and other aspects.

The Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA) in Northern Ireland reported shallow injection equipment can reduce ammonia emissions by 70-80 per cent, while in comparison the reduction with trailing hose is between 30 and 60 per cent. Correspondingly, the relative odour from shallow injection is low and it is moderate for trailing shoe and high for a splash plate. A trailing hose causes low crop damage, but shallow injection can lead to moderate crop damage. The capital cost of shallow injection equipment is much greater than for the splash plate or the trailing hose.

In addition, there are other non-soil management measures which can be undertaken by farmers to reduce ammonia emissions e.g. changing the diet of cattle, genetic improvement as well as the management of cattle when housed.

Recent studies on LESS in Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland provide further insights on the benefits and impacts of this soil management practice.

Lalor and Schulte (2008) reported that the trailing shoe method could be used for the greatest number of days compared to other LESS methods. This indicates that one benefit of LESS methods and the trailing shoe in particular can increase the opportunity to apply slurry during the spring.

Lalor et al. (2011) investigated if the use of trailing shoe (as an example of LESS) can increase the nitrogen fertilizer replacement value (NFRV) compared to a splash plate method. Thus, it was found that timing was important and slurry application in April rather than June can provide a significant increase in the nitrogen fertilizer replacement value.

McConnell et al. (2013a) studied both the trailing shoe and injection techniques and found that these LESS methods can reduce the concentration of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) during the period immediately after slurry application. In another related study McConnell et al. (2013b) found that allowing a grass sward to recover for at least 10 days post-harvest provides a potential mitigation strategy to reduce P losses in runoff following slurry application.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Precipitation

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil water content is critical for LESS methods. Therefore, the following soil properties are important: water holding capacity, ground water level, frequent water logging

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Excessive rainfall could limit the effectiveness of low emission slurry spreading.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

There is a need for further research to fully determine the potential area of low emission slurry spreading.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

There is a lack of evidence for most of the soil challenges which have been listed. therefore, it is difficult to be sure about the effects in every case.

Impacts

One issue is the safety of working with slurry.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

Holden, N. M., Fitzgerald, D., Ryan, D., Tierney, H., & Murphy, F. (2004). Rainfall climate limitation to slurry spreading in Ireland. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 122(3-4), 207-214.

Holden, N. M., Schulte, R. P. O., & Walsh, S. (2007). A slurry spreading decision support system for Ireland. In *Making Science Work on the Farm. A Workshop on Decision Support Systems for Irish Agriculture* (pp. 24-33). Agmet Dublin.

Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

Webb, J., Pain, B., Bittman, S., & Morgan, J. (2010). The impacts of manure application methods on emissions of ammonia, nitrous oxide and on crop response—a review. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 137(1-2), 39-46.

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

<https://www.hseni.gov.uk/articles/slurry-working-safely-slurry>

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
-

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.47 - Treatment of grassland/green manure crops with a nitrification inhibitor before incorporation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Treatment of grassland/green manure crops with a nitrification inhibitor before incorporation to reduce risk of N₂O emission

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

—
1
2
3
4
5
—

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes

Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

21 - Grassland with legumes

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P7 - Denmark (AU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

During the past 5-8 years, studies at AU have shown that nitrification inhibitor treatment of grass and clover immediately before incorporation by rotavation or ploughing can change the time course and extent of nitrification and N₂O emissions, which is mainly produced via denitrification. This has been shown at microcosm-, mesocosm- and field-scale (Duan et al., 2017; Kong et al., 2017; Kong et al., 2018). However, results under field conditions also show important interactions with soil conditions, in particular wetness. The treatment is probably most effective in well-drained or semi-dry soil, where de novo-production of nitrate is important to sustain denitrification associated with residue hotspots.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The treatment is probably most effective in well-drained or semi-dry soil, where de novo production of nitrate is important to sustain denitrification associated with residue hotspots.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Works probably best for well-drained soils.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA

2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	NA
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	NA
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	NA
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	NA
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.49 - Variable rate fertilizer application

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Variable rate technologies (VRT) allow site-specific management of parcels characterized by different levels of vigor and/or yield. Fertilizer VRT has the potential to improve and maximize efficiency of inputs and profitability of individual fields, by targeting application where needed and at optimum rates.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Concimazione a rateo variabile
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

30 - Inorganic fertilizers

Other one (if any)

1 - Conservation Agriculture

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P14 - Italy (CREA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Variable-rate fertilizer application allows farmers to apply different rates of fertilizer in each part of the field. There are different approaches of VRT fertilizer application, the mainly used that have been experimented in several areas is based on the quantitative characterization of intra-plot zones of a field, based on its yield potential, based on elaboration of series of satellite imagery.

Remotely sensed imagery of a field using a high-resolution constellation satellite was used to calculate the NDVI index (Vegetation index). The vigour map was computed using specific algorithm implemented by the engineering company, resulting in the segmentation of the field into different vigor classes, usually three: the low (L), medium (M) and high (H) vigor areas that were associated to the NDVI ranges. Thereafter, a prescription map was defined to implement a variable rate fertilization technique, adjusting N supply to each vigor level. Nitrogen fertilization was distributed through a variable-rate fertilizer spreader equipped with a GPS receiver and an automatic weighing system. Variable Rate Technology (VRT) has been recognised to be a promising tool helping farmers to decrease inputs of fertilizers, reducing in this way the farms’ costs, and consequently increasing incomes. The benefits can be the following: (i) All areas of the field receive the necessary amount of fertilizer. (ii) Potential increase in yields. More efficient fertilizer doses make increases more likely. (iii) Save the amount of fertilizer used, avoiding overspending in areas where nutrient removal is low. The main disadvantage of VRT fertilizer for farmer is the cost of machine.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors are not limiting

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : In Italy, organic soils are present in very small areas

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In agricultural soils there are no limiting factors

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	No Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

- Gatti et al., 2020. High potential of variable rate fertilization combined with a controlled released nitrogen form at affecting cv. Barbera vines behavior. European Journal of Agronomy, 112 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2019.125949>.
 - <https://agronotizie.imagelinenetwork.com/agrimeccanica/2019/03/28/concimazione-e-tempo-di-rateo-variabile/62353> (in Italian)
 - <http://fatima-h2020.eu/>
 - <https://www.ariespace.com/en/project/nutrisat-fertilization/>
-

References

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.50 - Forage legume-cereal double crop

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Forage legume-winter wheat double crop.

This technology recommends to keep the perennial legume swards for longer period and do not lose commercial production. In the first year, legume forage plant are sown into cereals, in the second year winter cereals are sown into legume forage plant by using the strip tillage and sowing method.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 double crop
 - 2 relay intercrop
 - 3 cropping system
 - 4 binary crop
 - 5 wide row
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected

Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

22 - Intercropping

Other one (if any)

50 - Strip tillage

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P16 - Lithuania (LAMMC)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early adopters
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Forage legume production is low on crop farms due to the limited use of the sward yield. Perennial forage legume is often grown for a short time (one year) as a in sown into cereals. However, the greater benefits of forage legume to the soil and agro-system are in growing them for a longer period of time (two years or more). Farmers on arable farms are not interested in separating a separate crop rotation field for forage legume and losing part of their marketable production. Usually, many farmers have grown cereals after the forage legume have been ploughed. This leads the mineralization of plant residues, which results in an increase in the N min amount in the soil during the non-plant vegetation period, and it is used inefficiently by crop rotation plants. Therefore, winter forage legume – cereal strip tillage intercropping with living or dead mulch technologies could optimize the mineralization of crop residues and increase productivity in the long term.

The studies were performed with forage legume black medic (*Medicago lupulina* L.), white clover (*Trifolium repens* L.), and Egyptian clover (*T. alexandrinum* L.) and winter cereals (*Triticum aestivum* L.). In the first-year forage legume were sown in oats., Before sowing winter wheat, after harvesting oats the forage legume mass was mulched on the soil surface. In the strip tillage system, a one-pass tillage, winter wheat seeding operations were performed using a Pro Till 3T hybrid machine manufactured by Mzuri, Great Britain. The row spacing was 0.33 m, the seeding depth was also 2.5–3.0 cm and it was seeded under a density of 380 wheat seeds m⁻². The use of this technique is suitable for sowing winter wheat in legumw swards. During sowing, the forage legume in the strips were uprooted and pushed into the

rows. The uprooted Egyptian clover played as a 'dead mulch', while the white clover and black medic regrow in spring (as living mulch) and competed with wheat.

In a binary cropping system, plant competition may be reduced when the aboveground mass of forage legume freezes during the winter (annual forage legume) or is mulched at the soil surface (perennial forage legume). Forage legume-cereal strip tillage intercrop technologies have been tested on farms by sowing winter triticale and rye into growing white clover. Increasing the diversity of plants in space creates conditions for the restoration / intensification of ecosystem services, therefore improves the cyclicity and uptake of nutrients, maintains soil fertility, optimizes the full use of their ecological services, spreads harmful organisms, and stabilizes plant productivity.

Under this practice, usually in the first year, cereal yields are decreasing compare to the conventional forage legume plough system. Nitrogen supply is a limiting factor in yields by reducing tillage.

In addition, it takes time for soil properties to stabilize and for organic carbon sequestration to increase the soil's capacity, to supply nitrogen by generating internal resources. Small farms are unable to buy strip tillage and sowing machines however cooperatives are being established.

The first data are presented in the articles (References and document section).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Unknown.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : Maybe if we choose the right plant combinations

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No data.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Plant species are selected according to suitable climatic conditions.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

The effect on plant yield is not immediately noticeable, it takes time to stabilize the soil properties.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

Böhm H., Dauber J., Dehler M., Gallardo D.A.A., de Witte T, Fuß R., Höppner F., Langhof M., Rinke N., Rodemann B., Rühl G., Schittenhelm S.2020.Crop rotations with and without legumes: a review (in German). *Journal für Kulturpflanzen*, 72 (10-11). S. 489–509, ISSN 1867-0911, DOI: 10.5073/JfK.2020.10-11.01

Inder Dev, Asha Ram, Sudesh Radotra, B.K. Misri, Sindhu Sareen, Pardeep Kumar, Deepak Singh, Sushil Kumar, Naresh Kumar, Ramesh Singh, Cereal clover bi-cropping for sustainable forage production in the Himalayan region, *European Journal of Agronomy*, Volume 130, 2021, 126354, ISSN 1161-0301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2021.126354>.

Layek J. et al. (2018) Cereal+Legume Intercropping: An Option for Improving Productivity and Sustaining Soil Health. In: Meena R., Das A., Yadav G., Lal R. (eds) *Legumes for Soil Health and Sustainable Management*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-0253-4_11

Jensen, E.S., Carlsson, G. & Hauggaard-Nielsen, H. Intercropping of grain legumes and cereals improves the use of soil N resources and reduces the requirement for synthetic fertilizer N: A global-scale analysis. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 40, 5 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-020-0607-x>

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

Böhm H., Dauber J., Dehler M., Gallardo D.A.A., de Witte T, Fuß R., Höppner F., Langhof M., Rinke N., Rodemann B., Rühl G., Schittenhelm S.2020.Crop rotations with and without legumes: a review (in German). *Journal für Kulturpflanzen*, 72 (10-11). S. 489–509, ISSN 1867-0911, DOI: 10.5073/JfK.2020.10-11.01

Bybee-Finley, K.A.; Ryan, M.R. Advancing Intercropping Research and Practices in Industrialized Agricultural Landscapes. *Agriculture* 2018, 8, 80. doi.org/10.3390/agriculture8060080

Layek J. et al. (2018) Cereal+Legume Intercropping: An Option for Improving Productivity and Sustaining Soil Health. In: Meena R., Das A., Yadav G., Lal R. (eds) Legumes for Soil Health and Sustainable Management. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-0253-4_11Sylvain Vrignon-Brenas, Florian Celette, Agnès Piquet-Pissaloux, Marie-Hélène Jeuffroy, Christophe David, Early assessment of ecological services provided by forage legumes in relay intercropping, *European Journal of Agronomy*, Volume 75, 2016, Pages 89-98, ISSN 1161-0301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2016.01.011>.

Jensen, E.S., Carlsson, G. & Hauggaard-Nielsen, H. Intercropping of grain legumes and cereals improves the use of soil N resources and reduces the requirement for synthetic fertilizer N: A global-scale analysis. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 40, 5 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-020-0607-x>

Impacts

Pittelkow CM, Linqvist BA, Lundy ME, Liang X, van Groenigen KJ, Lee J, van Gestel N, Six J, Venterea RT, van Kessel C (2015) When does no-till yield more? A global meta-analysis. *Field Crops Res* 183:156–168

Zikeli, S.; Gruber, S. Reduced Tillage and No-Till in Organic Farming Systems, Germany—Status Quo, Potentials and Challenges. *Agriculture* 2017, 7, 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture7040035>

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.51 - Swine manure biochar

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Swine manure biochar is produced from waste residues such as animalmanures. The feedstocks are pyrolyzed at 450 °C under limited oxygen conditions to produce biochar. Biochar is an approach to slow the release of nutrients, and thus protect the environment without compromising crop yield.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Biochar
 - 2 Charcoal
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

28 - Biochar

Other one (if any)

34 - Use of biofertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P16 - Lithuania (LAMMC)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Biochar is a valuable soil amendment. It has gained much attention in recent years for its ability to boost soil fertility and microbiology, upgrade soil structure, and accelerate plant growth. Mostly, charcoal biochar is produced from waste residues such as agricultural wastes, animal manures, and forest residues. Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry was used swine manure in study. Pig manure waste was obtained from an active animal husbandry. The manure was air-dried for 48 h, and grounded. The feedstocks were pyrolyzed at 450 °C in a muffle furnace for 4 h under limited oxygen conditions to produce biochar. Biochar can be useful to address challenges in crop and livestock agriculture. This manure has shown a significant decrease in nutrient leaching loss, greater retention of plant nutrients, and improvement in soil C and N compared with farmyard manure-treated soil. Biochar application increase the cation and anion exchange capacity of biochar, enable biochar to both adsorb and release nutrients to/from the soil, hence functioning as both a reservoir and slow-release source of plant nutrients. Researchers and farmers are have discovered many new uses for biochar, including: stormwater management and treatment; phosphorus traps to reduce water pollution; nitrogen traps to reduce ammonia and nitrate pollution; reclamation of mine tailings; building material blended with cement, mortar, plaster, etc.; electronic microwave shielding; electron storage and release as a “super-capacitor”, carbon fiber textiles for odor-absorbent clothing; carbon nanofibers to replace plastic and metal.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

There are no common climatic factors limiting the use of biochar. The interactive effects of biochar with precipitations amount on heavy metals stabilization in polluted soils. Drought moisture condition (5%) and optimum moisture (15%) enhance heavy metals in soil.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil moisture content is one of the most important soil properties that can affect the desorption and distribution of heavy metals among soil solid phases through its effect on soil redox potential, soil pH, changes in iron oxide species, mineralization rate and transformation of soil organic matter.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

Lichtfouse, E.; Navarrete, M.; Debaeke, P.; Souchère, V.; Alberola, C.; Ménassieu, J. Agronomy for sustainable agriculture: A review. In *Sustainable Agriculture*; Springer: Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 2009; pp. 1–7. DOI 10.1007/978-90-481-2666-8_1

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2013.773466>

Nair, V.D.; Nair, P.K.; Dari, B.; Freitas, A.M.; Chatterjee, N.; Pinheiro, F.M. Biochar in the agroecosystem–climate-change–

sustainability nexus. *Front. Plant. Sci.* 2017, 8, 2051. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2017.02051

Limiting soil factors

Shaheen, Sabry M., Nabeel Khan Niazi, Noha E. E. Hassan, Irshad Bibi, Hailong Wang, Daniel C. W. Tsang, Yong Sik Ok, Nanthi Bolan, and Jörg Rinklebe. 2019. “Wood-Based Biochar for the Removal of Potentially Toxic Elements in Water and Wastewater: A Critical Review.” *International Materials Reviews* 64(4):216–47. doi: 10.1080/09506608.2018.1473096

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.53 - Cover crop incorporation without herbicide application and ploughing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The shallow incorporation of plant residues or cover crops with a rotor, a cultivator or a shallow plough.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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1
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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	NA
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	NA

Water Management	NA
Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

15 - Cover crops

Other one (if any)

39 - Conservation tillage

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P24 - Switzerland (AGS)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Not relevant
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	early adopters
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The removal and incorporation of cover crops is a main challenge of reduced tillage approaches without herbicide application (e.g. in organic farming).

Multiple herbicide free practices to remove and incorporate cover crops are applied in Switzerland. The practices include (but are not limited to) a) the use of towed or semi-mounted cultivators with duck foot or wing tines operated at shallow depth, b) the use of short-disc harrows c) the use of horizontally rotating PTO-driven tillers, tine rotors or hoe rotors (e.g. the Geohobel ®) or d) the use of a skim plough (< 10 cm depth) (Dierauer & Leumann, 2018)

The application of cultivators (a) or skim ploughs (d) may need previous cutting of the cover crop. The short disc harrows (b) may be combined with a knife roller to crush and cut the cover crop. Some of the available farm equipment can be combined with tools for seedbed preparation and/or seeding machines. (Hegglin et al. 2014, Dierauer & Leumann, 2019; translated with KTBL, 2020)

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

It must be possible to grow cover crops (e.g. suitable length of the growing season)

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In clayey soils the use of PTO-driven units (e.g. tillers) or multiple runs of a cultivator can be advisable.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No

2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Adverse Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

The impact of herbicide-free reduced tillage in organic farming is the subject of many studies and reviews, such as Cooper et al. (2016) or Krauss et al. (2020). However, such studies often compare systems and not the effects of certain practices such as cover cropping. Additionally, some studies on cover crops focus on yield effect (e.g. Wittwer et al. 2017 and 2020) or do not consider the combination of cover crops with tillage practices (e.g. Adetunji et al., 2021). The impact statements above are to our best knowledge and judgment.

Impacts

A study by Wittwer et al. (2017) found that yields of maize and wheat in organic farming systems with reduced tillage were improved by cover crops. However, the yields were lower compared to plough based systems. A metastudy by Cooper et al. (2016) found that yields in reduced tillage systems are in average 7.6% lower compared to conventional ploughing but there were significant differences between treatments and experiments. The lower yields were partially attributed to reduced options for weed control in organic systems with reduced tillage and the resulting higher weed pressure. The same authors conclude that cover crop and residue management strategies have high potential to reduce weed pressure in reduced tillage systems. However, Dierauer & Leumann (2018) state that PTO-driven rotary machines can spread root-propagated weeds (e.g. *Cirsium arvense*).

Depending on the applied machinery and strategy costs for new machinery and/or increased workload may apply when cover crops are removed without ploughing and herbicide application.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

A Video of machine demo can be found here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZNjwI4xloGU>

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.54 - Legume-based green manure

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Additional processing of plant green mass (fermentation or composting) for plant fertilization.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 organic manure
 - 2 Green manure
 - 3 Compost
 - 4 Fermented plant mass
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

23 - Legume integration

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P16 - Lithuania (LAMMC)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early majority
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

In organic farms, the most important sources of nitrogen (N) are legume. Legume plants used as a green manure, the above-ground legume plants mass (especially forage legume) inserted into the soil decomposes quickly (not during the vegetation period of plants), therefore N does not stay in the soil for a longer time and adds organic matter into the soil reserves. Organic fertilizers made from legume plants mass can be stored until the next growing season and used for fertilising spring crops, while nitrogen and other nutrients can be used more efficiently on the farm - transferred from one to another field. Plant-based fertilisers are gaining exceptional value in conventional farms due to decline of livestock farms and the amount of manure produced.

At the end of June, legume-based organic fertilisers were produced from red clover mass (cut at the beginning of flowering stage) by ensiling or composting the mass with winter wheat straw. The compost was piled from two main components: aboveground mass of red clover (3 parts) and winter wheat straw (1 part). Aerobic composting was used; to stimulate decomposition the pile was mixed 5 times. The fermentation of red clover aboveground mass was performed as follows: the mass was cut, chopped, piled into a special trench and then pressed well to minimise the access to air as much as possible (or rolls can be produced). Having completed the piling, the mass was sealed with a special film as hermetically as possible. After 10 months in spring legume-based organic fertilisers were used as manure. The chemical composition of the legume-based green manure was as follows: fermented red clover mass: C – 392 kg t⁻¹ DM,

N – 19.0 kg t⁻¹ DM, P – 1.9 kg t⁻¹ DM, K – 17.2 kg t⁻¹ DM ir C:N = 35; red clover and straw compost: C – 514 kg t⁻¹ DM, N – 31.4 kg t⁻¹ DM, P – 6.8 kg t⁻¹ DM, K – 30.1 kg t⁻¹ DM ir C:N = 16. The energy consumption and cost of accumulated N and organic carbon loss during the fermentation of red clover mass were significantly lower than it was composted with straw. All inserted legume-based green manure increases the microbiological activity of the soil. The fermented mass increased biodiversity - the number of earthworms and the activity of insects useful for crops - and the amount of mobile humus substances. The fermented underground red clover mass is prepared in advance (earlier in the season). It is recommended to use the legume-based green manure thus prepared for spring fertilisation of spring cereals; it also benefits for growing cereals in the next year. This increases the nitrogen utilization efficiency of legume plants and soil viability. The incorporation of fermented red clover mass is useful due to N and other nutrients can be transferred from one crop rotation field to another or distributed to multiple crop rotation fields. Plant-based fertiliser production requires additional labour costs, suitable equipment. Preparation of treated plant mass for fertilisation and storage (drying, shredding, granulation, etc.) is not sufficiently absorbed.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

By selecting the components of plant mass, it is possible to produce the desired fertilizers of chemical composition. This allows to adapt to the soil, environmental conditions and the needs of the crops grown (fertilization time, methods).

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes

2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

Arlauskienė, A., Jablonskytė-Raščė, D., Šarūnaitė, L. et al. 2021. Perennial forage legume cultivation and their above-ground mass management methods for weed suppression in arable organic cropping systems. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture*. 8:34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40538-021-00228-5> sistemas

Carter M.S., Sørensen P., Petersen S.O., Ma X., Ambus P. 2014. Effects of green manure storage and incorporation methods on nitrogen release and N₂O emissions after soil application. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 50:1233–1246. DOI 10.1007/s00374-014-0936-5

Toleikienė M., Arlauskienė A., Šarūnaitė L., Šidlauskaitė G., Kadžiulienė Ž. 2020. The effect of plant-based organic fertilisers on the yield and nitrogen utilization of spring cereals in the organic cropping system. *Zemdirbyste-Agriculture*, 107(1): 17-24. http://www.zemdirbyste-agriculture.lt/1071_str3/

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...
-

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.56 - Biogas digestate and wood ash granulation and use as soil fertilizers

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

There are two by-products (digestate from biogas production and ash from heat and electricity cogeneration plant), mixing and granulation may be solution for new fertilizer.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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1
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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

Other one (if any)

30 - Inorganic fertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P15 - Latvia (UL)

Alpine North (ALN)	Yes
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Yes
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Yes
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Yes
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	Unknown
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Unknown
Atlantic North (ATN)	Unknown
Boreal (BOR)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	Unknown
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Unknown
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Unknown
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Unknown
Nemoral (NEM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Unknown

Specificities or further description of the practice

Digestate is the byproduct from the biogas production, where biowaste or other organic compounds undergoes anaerobic digestion. Digestate is rich in bioavailable macronutrients. However, these digestates need to be processed further to reach legislative compliance (Veneckhaute et al. 2014).

Wood ash is the byproduct of power plants, that at some rates were disposed in the landfills. Wood ash can be used in the agriculture as source of nutrient elements and lime (Demeyer et al. 2001).

Later research and investigation turn to the exploration of combining wood ash and digestate to improve gas production or to gain fertilizer applicable in agriculture.

There are few studies on wood ash and digestate combination, but benefits can be related to the more efficient digestion process to creation of new type of granular fertilizer (Abelenda & Aiouache, 2022; Pessonen et al. 2016)., that can improve soil properties (pH, nutrient N, NH₄⁺ NO₃ - content) (Juarez et al. 2013) promote crop growth (Ibeto et al. 2020) or release nutrients at controlled rate (Abelenda et al. 2021).

Technically this procedure must be applied in the reactor where abiotic digestion occurs. Wood ashes addition would stabilize pH in reactor, improve digestion process, lead to the formation and granulation of digestate through synergies of processes. The proposed wood ash addition is 5g wood ash total solids to 1 g digestate total solids (Abelenda et al. 2021).

In addition, some studies suggest, that combination of digestate and wood ashes may be used to improve degraded soils (Diatta et al. 2019).

The production of product with higher value will lead to the additional benefits in the farm who produce biogas.

However, there are still additional studies need to be completed to understand all possible gains from this practice.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Uncertain
gently sloping (2-5%)	Uncertain
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : There are no studies on impact between various soil types

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Uncertain
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

There is mentioned only one beneficial outcome in the project information. At the moment there is no precise information on practice benefits or adverse effects.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

<http://www.silava.lv/23/section.aspx/View/257>

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)**Documentation**

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.63 - Conservation agriculture

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

No-till, cover crops and a good crop rotation with the aim to disturb the soil less, always have a soil cover, and prolong the time with living roots in the soil.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Yes

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

No data

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P23 - Sweden (SLU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Yes
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not applied
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	Not applied
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early adopters
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

This answer is focused on grain producing farms.

Aspects of CA in Sweden.

A challenge with cover crops (CC) in Sweden is the short growing season that is shorter the further north you go. The growing season is limited by temperature and daylight. To ensure a good establishment of a CC they must generally be sown before the 15th of August. In the south of Sweden this is doable, but further north it is not, because the main crops have not been harvested by that time. Some farmers solve this by sowing the CC at the same time as they sow the main crop. Some sow the CC when they do the last weed-harrowing after emergence of the main crop (organic farms). Some have self-built machinery to sow the cover crop in the established stand of the main crop. Some accept this limit and only plan for CC after main crops that are harvested early.

Another challenge for CC is the regulations for receiving subsidies. They are limiting, and farmers find them a nuisance. The main points of criticism are: the dates for when a CC has to be sown and terminated are limiting, you cannot sow any species you want as a CC nor that you can sow a cocktail of species, you have to apply for subsidies that span over 5 years and must pay back the money received if a CC establishment fails, or the alternative subsidy which is only for one year but still has to be applied for in the spring and it is impossible to

know what the weather will be like in August when it is time to sow the cover crops. So, the farmer must be conservative and not apply for the whole potential area and therefore miss opportunities if the weather at the end of the summer does permit establishment of CC.

There are a few organically certified farmers that are interested in CA and strive to achieve this without the use of herbicides. They are often inspired by cropping systems from Germany and Austria. The challenge with CA in organic production is to achieve no-till without increasing the perennial weeds over time, and to terminate the CC. In conventional systems this is done by herbicide applications. One solution is to do a shallow (5 cm deep) pass with a rotary tiller. The sward of the CC is cut off and in dry weather the cut off parts will dry down and the C is successfully terminated.

Some farmers combine this with a treatment of a lactic acid bacteria solution (fermented molasses and water). The low pH (3,5) in the solution combined with the activity of the lactic acid bacteria further breaks down the CC residue. After 7-14 days the CC is dead, and the main crop can be sown.

The system with terminating cover crops by using a roller crimper (e.g used at Rodale institute in the U.S) is generally considered to not work under Swedish conditions since the main crops (small grain cereal) must be planted before the cover crop is mature enough to be roller-crimped. However, it might work for vegetable production in Sweden.

CA is not widespread in Sweden. But there is a growing interest in soil health and alternative farming methods in Sweden as well as globally. Many farmers practicing CA seek a lot of knowledge themselves from youtube and facebook. Many also travel to international conferences mainly in the U.K or USA. These farmers are often frustrated with the knowledge they find from institutions in Sweden (universities,the crop consultants). They feel that these institutions are not up to date with current knowledge and that they cannot receive advice that is adequate within CA.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

A challenge with cover crops (CC) in Sweden is the short growing season that is shorter the further north you go. The growing season is limited by temperature and daylight. To ensure a good establishment of a CC they must generally be sown before the 15th of August. In the south of Sweden this is doable, but further north it is not, because the main crops have not been harvested by that time. Some farmers solve this by sowing the CC at the same time as they sow the main crop. Some sow the CC when they do the last weed-harrowing after emergence of the main crop (organic farms). Some have self-built machinery to sow the cover crop in the established stand of the main crop. Some accept this limit and only plan for CC after main crops that are harvested early.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Stone content of the soil might be limiting.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	NA
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

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Other general comments

For terminating cover crops with rotary-tiller and applicatio of lactic acid bacteria see p 10-13 here: <https://okologi-kongres.dk/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/F1-MartinBeck.pdf>

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.64 - Evaluation of the effect of buffer strips on nutrient leaching

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Grass buffer strips effectively reduced the leaching of particulate phosphorus and nitrogen

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Skyddszoner
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected

Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Yes
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

3 - Buffer strips

Other one (if any)

3 - Buffer strips

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P23 - Sweden (SLU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	early majority
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

A Field experiment to investigate nutrient leaching was established in 2011 on a clay loam. The field site is located about 15 km south of Uppsala in eastern Sweden (59°43'0'' N; 17°41'21'' E). The experimental field is about 0.42 ha (72 × 50 m), with a slope in the north-south direction of about 1%. At the lower part of the field, grassed buffer strips were established as follows: A) Control, which is managed in the same way as the main field; B) Grass buffer strips; C) As B, but the grass harvested once a year. Each treatment was 6 m by 6 m, and is replicated in four blocks. Each plot is drained with a central 6-m long drain pipe at 1 m depth. The rest of the field is not drained. Surface runoff and drainage water are led to an automated measuring and sampling station. The samples were analyzed for phosphorus, nitrogen and organic carbon. On average, the leaching of particulate phosphorus via drainage tiles was reduced by 17 % in the grass buffer strips but the effect of harvesting the grass on reducing leaching was very little. Nitrate leaching was reduced by 28 %. Surface runoff was scarce during the experimental years and its data was insufficient to draw conclusions.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

NO

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

No data

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)**Documentation**

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.65 - Structure liming enhances aggregate stability and gives varying crop responses on clayey soils

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The research results indicate that structure liming can be used as a measure to mitigate phosphorus losses from clayey soils, thereby preventing eutrophication of nearby waters.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

—
1
2
3
4
5
—

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected

Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	Soil structure improvement

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

31 - Liming

Other one (if any)

31 - Liming

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P23 - Sweden (SLU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

No data

Specificities or further description of the practice

Associated nutrients. Two types of structure lime, slaked lime ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) and a mixed product of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and slaked lime ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), were applied at three different rates in field trials on clayey soils (23%–40% clay). A combination of primary tillage and structure liming was also studied, in a split-plot trial on a clayey soil (25% clay). Aggregate (2–5 mm) stability, measured as reduction in turbidity (which is strongly correlated with losses of particulate phosphorus), was significantly increased with the highest application rates of both structure lime products. Aggregate size distribution was also improved with structure lime, creating a finer tilth in the seedbed. Yield response to structure lime was not consistent, with both negative and positive responses over the four-year study period. Positive yield responses can possibly be attributed to the finer tilth preventing evaporation in two dry growing seasons. Negative yield responses were probably an effect of impaired phosphorus availability associated with limited precipitation in May–July in 2011 and 2013. Two years after liming, soil pH levels were significantly elevated in plots with the highest application rate of structure lime, whereas no significant increases were found three years after liming. However, a lingering effect of liming was still detectable, as manganese concentration in barley grain was significantly lower in plots with the highest application rates of both structure lime products in the fourth study year. These results indicate that structure liming can be used as a measure to mitigate phosphorus losses from clayey soils, thereby preventing eutrophication of nearby waters. However, the yield response was varying and unpredictable and thus further investigations are needed to determine the circumstances in which field liming can act efficiently not only to prevent phosphorus losses, but also to ensure consistent yield increases.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Weather conditions can affect the measures. For example, application of the calcium hydroxide in cold weather does not improve soil structure

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

This measure is only for soils with approximately 15% clay content

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA

2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	NA
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.66 - Integrated Constructed Wetland

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The use of an Integrated Constructed Wetland (ICS) on an intensive dairy farm to primarily treat soiled water, typically removing through flowing organic matter, nitrogen and phosphorus to ensure the protection of receiving waters and flood attenuation. The ICS can provide a number of other ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Constructed Wetland
2	
3	
4	
5	

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

5 - Retention ponds

Other one (if any)

52 - Drainage systems, water table management and flooding

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P13 - Ireland (Teagasc)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

With increasing pressure on farmers to reduce sediment and nutrient losses to water, land owners are looking to alternative methods such as the use of an Integrated Constructed Wetland (ICW). ICW’s are a recognized form of wastewater treatment that have been used to treat varying types of polluted water including those of industrial, domestic, and agricultural origin (Kadlec & Knight 1996). They can filter and remove high levels of sediment, nitrogen and phosphorus from wastewater. ICW’s are usually made up of a primary settlement tank where wastewater is collected, several ponds follow which are planted with wetland plants. The ponds are usually gently sloped towards a river to allow water to flow very slowly through the wetland. Particles that have been carried in the water will settle on the bottom and the plants and natural microorganisms will break down and remove nutrients.

The current regulations in Ireland allow for slightly soiled water (grey water) to be piped from a hard surface area which is cleaned regularly directly into a river which can negatively affect water quality if the hard area is not managed correctly. Installing an ICW can mitigate against issues or mistakes that might arise depending on management and weather conditions.

At present, the main input into an ICW is from farmyards. Research has found that an ICW can be very effective in trapping sediment and nutrients from other sources also. A number of catchments in Ireland have sediment and phosphorus issues due to the poorly draining soil in the area. The EPA have developed a mapping system where we can identify overland flow paths and delivery points where water runs over land and enters a river. ICW’s have the potential to be strategically placed in the landscape to intercept overland flow, slowing down the flow of water leading to reduced erosion and sediment loss.

The current regulation in Ireland allows farmers to spread soiled water on the land at any time during the year, if spread at the incorrect time or location this can lead to pollution incidents. The use of an ICW would minimize this practice leading to improved water quality.

As an ICW is designed to look and function as a natural wetland, the co-benefits are improved biodiversity on an intensive farm and the potential to sequester carbon.

Farmers like: Soiled water as defined in the nitrates regulations is allowed to enter an ICW for treatment. Rather than allowing lightly soiled water to run directly into a river (which is compliant with regulations) with the potential to cause a decline in water quality, a farmer can use an ICW to remove sediment and nutrients.

This type of water management can also help to control the flow of water running into a river, causing flooding issues downstream at lower points on the farm. If a farmer is allowed to put soiled water into an ICW rather than having to spread it on the land, this leads to reduced labor and spreading costs.

Many farmers are also becoming interested in carbon storage and biodiversity, having an ICW on the farm can help to improve both.

Farmers dislike: The substantial cost of installation and the amount of land required to ensure it works correctly. Planning permission/discharge licence is required to install an ICW and regular monitoring of the water quality at the outlet is also required to ensure the system is working. The ICW must also be inspected and maintained every 5-10 years to ensure it continues to function correctly which can also be costly.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Uncertain
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil texture and depth to rock as water may be lost to groundwater

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	NA
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

If soil is very free draining, a liner can be used instead or a soil type with a higher clay content can be used.

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.67 - Subsurface drainage

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Drainage systems, water table management and flooding”: Process of directing excess water away from root zones by natural or artificial means

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 drainage
 - 2 ditch
 - 3 drainage
 - 4 diking
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

52 - Drainage systems, water table management and flooding

Other one (if any)

52 - Drainage systems, water table management and flooding

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P23 - Sweden (SLU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	early adopters
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	early adopters
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Land drainage is removal of excess surface and subsurface water from land to enhance crop growth, including the removal of soluble salts from the soil.

The aim of land drainage is to optimize agricultural production related to:

conservation of agricultural land

reclamation of agricultural land

optimization of crop yield

crop diversification

cropping intensification

optimisation of farm operations

A subsurface drainage system includes a drainage outlet, main drainage channel, some collector drains and field or lateral drains. The main drainage channel collects runoff from one or more collector drains. It discharges its water via a pumping station or by gravity into a river, a lake, or the sea at a suitable outlet. The main drainage channel is often a canal stream, which runs

through the lowest parts of the agricultural area. Both collectors and lateral drains can be open ditches or pipe drains.

A controlled drainage system involves a control structure in main channel or in the outlet. The control structure can be raised or lowered depending on the drainage demand. A controlled drainage system can be used to control the watertable during the season to meet the drainage demand. The system can be regarded as a measure to save water and nutrient in the soil for crop uptake during the growing season.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No climatic limitations

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	No
sloping (5-10%)	No
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Clay content < 10% at 0-100 cm depth, the soil needs to have a drainage demand

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	NA
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	NA
Enhance soil biodiversity	NA
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.71 - Variable rate irrigation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

It is a sprinkler irrigation technique that allows the water doses to be modulated at each nozzle or group of nozzles on the equipment. It aims to optimize water application by taking into account the variability of the environment and particularly soils or crop development. The technique can apply for water and what can be transported by water like fertilizers and when authorized some pest control products.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Variable rate irrigation management
 - 2 Site-specific irrigation management
 - 3 Site-specific variable rate sprinkler irrigation systems
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected

Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

54 - Irrigation scheduling

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P1 - France (INRAE)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Yes
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The variable rate irrigation (VRI) technology is a sprinkler irrigation system allowing the modulation of the flow rate of the nozzles, via the opening of solenoid valves, allowing different zones to be irrigated (zone control). It exists on center pivots and linear move systems. The size of the zone may vary depending on the specifics of the equipment. Water rates are controlled by on-board computer connected with a GPS system and in which the user records a zoning based on the identification of homogeneous zones (soil and plant maps) and specific prescriptions. The objective of the precision irrigation systems is to improve water and N-fertilizers use efficiency, i.e. quantity (and quality) of agricultural biomass produced for each cubic meter of irrigation water or N-fertilizer supplied. The objective of VRI technology is to optimize water use according to the soil variability and the culture.

Implementing this type of precision irrigation requires mapping the characteristics of the soil (depth, water balance, texture) as well as the biomass of the crop in order to estimate its water and N-nutrient requirements according to its location in the plot. The prescription maps constructed will pilot the modulation system in order to adapt the inputs to the real needs of the crop. The use of this technology is accompanied by the installation of sensors on the agricultural plot: tensiometric probes, capacitive probes and weather stations, or observation methods (airborne images).

This type of equipment is advantageous more specifically in contexts where the volume of water available for irrigation is limited: quotas, restrictions, irrigation water storage. The

most profitable situations concern large field with heterogeneous soils or crop development. Soil or crop heterogeneities scale that can be considered is ranging from 0.1 to 0.5ha.

Nevertheless, precision irrigation is not much developed in France at the present time, due to the technical nature of their implementation. The main difficulty of implementation is the lack of operational tools making the link between the maps (geophysics, soil, crop, satellites) and the irrigation or N-nutrient dose to be provided, that is to say a tool for building the homogeneous command areas (site specific variable rate irrigation prescriptions). Secondly, the initial investment is very important with high marginal costs with uncertainty about the real benefits they bring to the farmer. Irrigators in France do not have the tools to assess the potential water savings achievable by using the VRI technology. There are few documentary references to prove the gains associated with this technology. Basic and applied research is needed to provide guidance on how to best define the economic number and size of agronomic management zones for different levels and types of VRI systems.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Wind speed or direction

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : There is no study on the use of VRI in organic soils/peatlands.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil infiltration capacity < irrigation flow

The most profitable situations concern large field with heterogeneous soils (mainly texture).

Soil or crop heterogeneities scale that can be considered is ranging from 0.1 to 0.5ha.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The most profitable situations concern large field with heterogeneous soils. Soil heterogeneity must have large structures.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.72 - IRRISAT: irrigation scheduling through Remote Sensing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The methodology is based on innovative technology that integrates satellite observations with high spatial and temporal weather forecasts. Using original calculation codes, Irrisat allows to view maps of daily irrigation requirements, starting with the last irrigation made and with a forecast up to five days later. The system, moreover, through simple and intuitive screens, allows to carry out analysis on the state of the crop and weather data (evapotranspiration, irrigation, rain, temperature, vegetation indices).

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Irrigation suggestion and advice
 - 2 Irrigation guided by Satellite information
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

54 - Irrigation scheduling

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P14 - Italy (CREA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	early adopters
Mediterranean South (MDS)	early adopters
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Sustainable management of water resource require reliable estimation of crop evapotranspiration (ET) and irrigation water requirements (IWR) at field level with high spatial and temporal resolution. Soil water balance (SWB) models present limitations when applied to wide areas due to complexity of input data required, with special concern to soil hydraulic properties, interaction with groundwater, variability of plant development due to different crop varieties and management practices.

The methodology is based on the application of FAO Penman-Monteith (FAO-56 PM) procedure for the calculation of potential evapotranspiration (ET_c) (Allen et al., 1998). Basically the calculation of ET_c requires standard meteorological data, such as temperature and relative humidity of the air, solar radiation,

average wind speed, and the crop characteristic parameters that influence the entity of evapotranspiration fluxes (e.g. the leaf area index LAI and surface albedo. In the IRRISAT methodology those crop parameters are calculate from Remote Sensing Images in the Visible and Near Infrared spectral region. IWR (Vanino et al, 2018 DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rs.e.2018.06.035>.)

The system (web-based) provides efficient planning of irrigation volumes and times to ensure the minimum consumption of water for the same production, obtaining the following advantages:

Reducing water and energy waste

Optimizing production and work

Real-time monitoring of crop development

Updated weather information

The system is developed by the Ariespace S.r.l. Spin-Off company dell'Università di Napoli Federico II (<https://www.irisat.com/en/home-2#contact>), within the Rural development Programme (RDP) 2014-2020 of the Campania Region. The aim of the system is to help farmer to Adherence to the Regional Irrigation Advisory Plan for the calculation of the water balance, which is one of Eligibility conditions to comply with the provisions on irrigation contained in the integrated production regulations of the Campania Region, which are essential for adhering to Measure 10 (agri-environmental measure) and Measure 4.1.4 (Management of water resources for irrigation purposes on farms) of the RDP 2014-2020.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

There are no climatic factors limit to the application of this practice. Usually some irrigation systems are put in the field only during the crop growing season to not deteriorate the tool during winter period when it's not used.

Where precipitations are good and there are no water stress during summer period, it's not necessary to irrigate (e.g. when the Standardized Precipitation Index - SPI > -1 , which means PRECIPITATION REGIME from Moderately wet ($1.0 < \text{SPI} \leq 1.5$), to Extremely wet ($2.0 < \text{SPI} \leq \text{MAX}$)).

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Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping ($< 2\%$)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep ($> 60\%$)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

SPI>-1.0 No IRRIGATION

SPI (Standardized precipitation Index)

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

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Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

World Meteorological Organization. 2012. Standardized Precipitation Index User Guide. (M. Svoboda, M. Hayes and D. Wood). WMO-No. 1090. Geneva. ISBN 978-92-63-11091-6. 16p.

Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

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Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)**Documentation**

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.73 - Relay intercropping

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Relay Intercropping is the practice of growing two or more different crops, with different growth characteristics and development requirements, in the same season and the same field. In Switzerland, the practice is applied with winter wheat and soybean.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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1
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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	NA
Tillage and traffic	NA
Crop protection	NA
Water Management	NA

Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

26 - Strip cropping

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P24 - Switzerland (AGS)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Not relevant
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

In the relay intercropping system, two or more crops grow simultaneously in the same field for a certain period of their growing season. Universities in the U.S. have been studying and developing relay intercropping for several decades.

In relay intercropping, winter cereals are sown like a row crop, with spacing between them similar to tramlines. The soybeans are sown into the rows in spring and grow beneath the cereals until the cereal harvest. The winter cereal shades the soybean, optimally enough to prevent weeds from germinating but without hindering the development of the soybean too severely.

Later, after the grain is cut high, the soybeans develop throughout the summer and fall months.

Relay intercropping allows to optimize the utilization of the growing season to grow biomass and increase the productivity per area and year. The longer crop growth provides permanent soil cover with living plants until the soybean harvest. Furthermore, it is assumed to reduce weed pressure and thus herbicide use. It is also assumed, that relay intercropping allows increased nutrient use efficiency, by a) complementary nutrient needs of the intercropped crops and b) by fixation of N by leguminous crops, such as soybean.

However, Hartschuh (2019) suggests the significant drawbacks of relay intercropping are its dependence on favorable climatic conditions for two crops. Furthermore, relay intercropping relies on very timely field operations and adapted, supposedly costly, machinery.

Ongoing field trials on seven Swiss farms will assess the potential of relay intercropping in European conditions (IG Relay Intercropping, 2021). Findings from relay intercropping trials have also been reported from other European Countries (e.g. wheat and forage legume intercropping in France; Vrignon-Brenas et al. (2016))

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Vegetation period must sustain both crops, e.g. winter wheat and soya.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Not adaptable to droughty, poorly drained, or very heavy clay soils

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

Mechanical weed control is limited in the rows, therefore weed control in organic farming is challenging.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

The two overlapping crops increase the nutrient use efficiency and provide permanent soil cover, either directly by the living plants or by the plant residues. It seems plausible that this in turn reduces erosion, and leads to enhanced soil structure and increased microbial activities and diversity. The increased biomass production could lead to higher SOM inputs and thus to higher SOC. How the higher input of SOM affects greenhouse gas emissions remains unknown. In any case, we reviewed no evidence on the claimed effects on the soil.

Impacts

Long-term experiments in the US showed that intercropped wheat yields are typically about 90% of pure wheat. Soybean harvest can potentially compensate the reduced yield and the extra costs for seeding. However, experiments in the US suggest that the soybean yield is susceptible to environmental conditions (e.g. drought in summer, early frost) and consequently highly variable ranging from 0 t/ha to 3.8 t/ha with an average of 2.3 t/ha (Hartschuh, 2019).

Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

Hartschuh (2019)

Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

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Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.74 - Cascade use of biochar in animal husbandry and plant production

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The combined and subsequent use of biochar in animal husbandry and as fertilizer component or soil amendment in plant production.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	NA
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	NA
Crop protection	NA

Water Management	NA
Agricultural Systems	NA
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	NA
NA	Soil improvement product

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

28 - Biochar

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P24 - Switzerland (AGS)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	early adopters
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	early adopters
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Besides direct soil application, biochar is used as an amendment in many processes linked to animal husbandry. According to Schmidt (2012), biochar is directly added to animal feed (e.g. silage). It may also be applied as part of stable beddings or directly into the slurry reservoir. Furthermore, biochar can be used as a compost additive, either by mixing it into the compost heap, or via compostable organic substances from stable beddings, like manure or the solid product of slurry separation.

An extensive review of the effects of biochar in animal husbandry by Schmid et al. (2019) reported many benefits of its application. In the silage, biochar can reduce mycotoxin formation, bind pesticides, suppress butyric acid formation and enhance the quantity of lactic bacteria. In the stable bedding, biochar is reported to reduce hoof diseases, odors and nutrient losses. As an additive to slurry it is said to reduced odors, surface crusts and nutrient losses. Throughout these cascades, the biochar becomes enriched with nutrients. Furthermore, both water storage capacity and nutrient exchange capacity of the biochar are increased during the cascade use. The authors claim that by the cascade use biochar becomes a more efficient plant growth enhancing soil amendment that improves the recycling of nutrients from organic residues of animal farming.

When biochar is applied in animal husbandry, it typically arrives at the field surface as dung, manure, slurry or compost. The soil organisms incorporate the biochar into the soil (Schmidt et al. 2021). However, for optimal effect in plant production, biochar should be placed in the root zone of the plants or should be incorporated into the soil (5 to 30 cm). Left at the soil surface it could be washed away by water or blown away by wind (erosion).

Biochar for animal husbandry typically is of premium quality. Today, there are voluntary industry standards, such as the EBC-label (www.european-biochar.org) to ensure high quality, pollutant-free biochar production.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Beneficial Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

A review of meta-studies by Schmidt et al. 2021 found positive effects on soils for all reviewed parameters, except for CH₄ emissions from soils (see figure). However, there is substantial evidence that CH₄ emissions in animal husbandry can be reduced by biochar application in silage, feedstuff or stable bedding. In any case, no full cascade greenhouse gas emission study was found and reviewed by Schmidt et al., (2019).

Impacts

A recent metastudy by Schmidt et al. (2021) summarizes the beneficial effects of biochar on plants, yields and farm economics (see figure). Another review by Schmidt et al. (2019) concludes that the use of biochar as a feed additive has the potential to improve animal health, feed efficiency and livestock productivity, as well as to reduce nutrient losses and greenhouse gas emissions. In regard to animal safety, they state that biochar feeding can be considered safe at least for feeding periods of several months. However, they stress that despite their positive assessment, regular feeding of biochar should never induce livestock farmers to compromise on the quality of feed and animal welfare standards. Nowadays, the application of biochar seems to be restrained by the costs of about 700 euros per ton of biochar (Schmidt et al., 2021).

Other general comments

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References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

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Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

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NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.76 - Multifunctional cover crop

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A multifunctional cover crop is adapted for the specific site and situation in order to provide one or more functions

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 catch crop
 - 2 Intermediate crop
 - 3 Intercrop
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Yes

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

15 - Cover crops

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P23 - Sweden (SLU)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Yes
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Yes
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	early adopters
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

A cover crop is grown between two main crops, during summer, autumn and winter. It can be undersown in spring or sown after harvest of the main crop. Perennial or annual grasses, herbs or cereals are common cover crops, often used for reducing N leaching over winter. Cover crops is not a new concept, and are widely implemented in parts of Northern Europe. There is an increasing interest in agriculture for their multifunctions which turns cover crops into innovative concepts. Such interests include biomass production for harvest or for carbon storage in the soil, to provide pathogen suppression or green manure by fixing N. Cover crops is an essential part of conservation and regenerative agriculture, where continuous crop cover is essential and where farmers make experimental development of new systems.

Farmers interest for undersown cover crops of pure grasses has declined despite financial support in e.g. Sweden and their robust function for reducing N leaching and carbon sequestration. To find other functional species and species mixtures are of great interest among farmers, where possible benefits can be identified and utilized to improve cropping systems. However, there are challenges at northern altitudes, where there is a short autumn for growth which constrains the amount of possible species.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The length of the crop growth period limits the amount of species and the time period when it is possible to use for the cover crop in Northern part of Europe

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA

2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	No Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

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Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

Aronsson H, Hansen E M, Thomsen I K, Liu, J, Øgaard A F, Känkänen H, Ulén B. 2016. The ability of cover crops to reduce nitrogen and phosphorus losses from arable land in southern Scandinavia and Finland – a review. *Journal of Soil and water Conservation* 71 (1): 41-55. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.71.1.41>

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

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Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

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Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.77 - Agroforestry

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Agroforestry is a human made ecosystem that combines forestry with agriculture and/or livestock by incorporating various ecosystem elements into time and space. Agroforestry usually has social benefits as well, next to economic and environmental benefits. It can be defined as “the practice of deliberately integrating woody vegetation (trees or shrubs) with crop and/or livestock production systems to benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions”, according to H2020 AGFORWARD project. This definition is similar to those adopted by the World Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF), the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), and the Association for Temperate Agroforestry (AFTA). For the first time, Lundgren and Raintree in 1982 explained that in agroforestry systems there are both ecological and economic interactions and defined those systems as “a collective name for a land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials are deliberately used on the same land-management unit as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial and temporal arrangement”.

In 1992, Sommariba defines agroforestry as a form of multiple cropping which satisfies at least three basic conditions:

1. There are at least two species that interact biologically
2. At least one of the species is a woody perennial
3. At least one of the plant species is managed for forage, annual or perennial crop production.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Agroforestry
2	agro-selviculture
3	Silvo-pastoral system
4	Agro-silvo-pastoral system; silvo-arable;
5	Mixed and inter crops (herbaceous and woody crops)

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Yes
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

22 - Intercropping

Other one (if any)

17 - Crop rotation

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P14 - Italy (CREA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected

Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Yes
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean North (MDN)	early adopters
Mediterranean South (MDS)	early adopters
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Italy has 1.4 million ha under agroforestry, covering about 11% of the total utilised agricultural area. At European level, Italy represents the fourth largest area for livestock agroforestry systems and the second largest area for silvoarable and agroforestry with high value trees. Due to the several agro-environmental zones (from Alpine South to Mediterranean South), Italy has a wide range of agroforestry systems, which are often rich in biodiversity. These wide range of agroforestry systems can favor diversified landscapes, valuable for recreation and tourism. The agroforestry systems in Italy and associated innovations are considered in terms of silvopastoral system, olive trees and arable production systems. As innovative strategy, agroforestry

certification is also considered. Silvopastoral systems refer to the integration of trees in livestock farms or to the use of livestock in woody crops such as forests (e.g. forest grazing) or orchards (e.g. olive groves). Currently, about 10.1% of the Italian utilised agricultural area is managed by silvopastoral systems that integrate trees with livestock production, mainly in marginal areas. The most important benefits of these systems include mitigation of GHG emissions, livestock adaptability to climate change, and the increase of nutritional quality of livestock products. Other positive examples of biodiversity increase can be given such as beneficial insects and opportunities for larger animals. In order to prevent overgrazing to favor forest regeneration, the grazing pressure can be reduced by using rotational, mixed or precision grazing. In the Alpine South, wood pasture is typically semiextensive and grazed by cattle. The structure includes both low-density tree populations and mosaics of small woods among pastures and shrubland. The larch wood pasture is a traditional system with high landscape and ecological values, which integrates cattle, sheep, pasture, and timber production. Moreover, in this zone, there is a growing interest in goat grazing in forests, due to the increase in dairy goat products. In the Apennines (Med Mountainns), the main agro-silvopastoral systems are based on extensive and semi-extensive management for small herds of sheep and beef cattle, grazing continuously or moved to forest clearings and wood pastures from the end of spring to the beginning of autumn depending on the altitude and environmental conditions. The sheep grazing in firebreaks lines has received growing interest because it aims at preventing shrub ingressions.

In recent decades, the olive agroforestry (i.e. olive trees intercropped with other crops and/or grazed) has been increasingly recommended and adopted, both

to prevent soil erosion and soil degradation and to increase biodiversity. Agroforestry on arable lands can improve land productivity, reduce pollution and address climate change by sequestering more carbon than conventional arable systems. Agroforestry certification requires the establishment of sustainable management criteria and guidelines. Well-managed agroforestry systems can also provide opportunities to minimize land abandonment. Regarding the farmers' perception of agroforestry systems, they agree that the effects of agroforestry on production and the environment were generally positive, whilst those related to management were generally negative. Farmers perceived positively the business opportunities from adopting agroforestry because multifunctional systems and diversification increase agricultural resilience.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No climatic factors limit the application of agroforestry in the Mediterranean and Alpine South environments.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : Favoring peatland restoration

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Unknown Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

The permanent agroforestry systems maintain a continuous cover that reduces evapotranspiration and salts accumulation in topsoils. Generally they increase soil quality and fertility, by also reducing soil GHG emissions (e.g., carbon sequestration and reducing N₂O emissions) as well as degradation of peatlands.

Impacts

Adaptation to climate change, maintenance/enhancement of wildlife habitat, economic benefits for farmers by using fodder, and tree by-products.

Other general comments

<https://www.agforward.eu/>

<http://www.agroforestry.it/> (in Italian)

<https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/countries/italy>

<https://www.enicbcmed.eu/projects/livingagro>

Paris P, Camilli F, Rosati A, Mantino A, Mezzalira G, Dalla VC, Franca A, Seddaiu G, Pisanelli A, Lauteri M, Brunori A, Re GA, Sanna F, Ragaglini G, Mele M, Ferrario V, Burgess PJ (2019) What is the future for agroforestry in Italy? *Agroforest Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00346-y>

Camilli F, Pisanelli A, Seddaiu G, Franca A, Bondesan V, Rosati A, Moreno GM, Pantera A, Hermansen JE, Burgess PJ (2018) How local stakeholders perceive agroforestry systems: an Italian perspective. *Agrofor Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0127-0>

References

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.79 - Species-rich inter-row covering

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The role of species-rich inter-row grass planting techniques in improving soil conditions and enhancing biodiversity, with particular regard to plant protection and defense against erosion.

Climate change is expected to increase the frequency of extreme weather events, such as extended periods of heat and drought in summer, and sudden, heavy precipitation. These phenomena can increase the risk of soil depletion and erosion, especially on sloping ground, making it advisable to plant well-chosen and well-maintained plants in the spaces between rows of perennial crops. By using carefully selected species, we can not only increase the conservation value of the area, but also promote good soil structure (rooting types), nutrient replenishment (leguminous varieties) and provide habitats for beneficial organisms (e.g. predatory mites, spiders).

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Yes
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

16 - Cover crops in permanent crops

Other one (if any)

48 - Reduced tillage in permanent crops

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P12 - Hungary (MTA ATK)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected

Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes
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Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	few farmers (“innovators”)

Specificities or further description of the practice

What does the seed mixture consist of?

The plant species that make up the mixture are: *Medicago Lupuliana* (30%), *Lotus corniculatus* (25%), *Trifolium repens* (25%), *Plantago lanceolata* (10%), *Securigera varia* (5%), *Daucus carota* (5%).

Expected results:

The publication of a technical manual for farmers on the applicability of biodiverse inter-row planting for the sustainable protection of grape plants.

The development, product design and commercialization of a new, ground-covering, inter-row seed mixture in fruit producing areas.

Scientific publications. A technical publication on the effects of soil management strategies on soil condition and biodiversity in viticulture and fruit production.

Further training for expert advisors on optimal soil management methods adapted to local growing conditions.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Can it be used on clayey, bound soils?

In Hungary they have many years of experimental experience on clay soil, Balatonfőkajár, where the plant species that make up the mixture have developed successfully. To use our mixture, it is necessary for the grape grower to be able to sow 1-3 cm deep (and not deeper), in a smaller area e.g. it is advisable to rake the seeds. So it's not enough to just spray the mixture on the soil, it's not necessarily enough. If the 'Live Row Spacing' seed mixture is sown by the farmer in the traditional sense, according to the former, germination also takes place on clay soil. What you need to know is that the rate of germination and settlement depends on the local plant flora as well as the weed seed stock of the soil.

Is it possible to use this seed mixture in conventional buck grapes?

Seed mixture is less recommended for buck grapes. Because the cluster zone is low in this cultivation method, there is not as much free space here as in a cordon plantation. It is usually

also rolled in cordon grapes when approx. the vegetation between the rows reaches the height below the knee. If it is mown at or before flowering, it will prevent seeding and the cover will not be as effective for several years. The other options depend largely on the area's original vegetation cover.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	NA
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

Can the seed mixture be suitable for row spacing in orchards or on sandy soils?

Yes, we have already tried our seed mixture in grapes on sandy soil and it has worked there as well. As far as planting in the orchard is concerned, the beneficial effects on the soil and the plant are of course also present in this case, e.g. through species richness, as plant species with different rooting types and depths contribute to the reduction of soil compaction, the formation of crumbly, favorable soil structure, and the increase of humus content. With living ground cover, we also provide living space for useful living organisms. However, it is important to mention one thing: bees are attracted to flowering vegetation and in this case insecticides used in orchards, even those used in organic farming, harm pollinating insects, so their use should be reconsidered and not used in flowering flocks.

Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

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Impacts

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Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

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Farming systems

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Limiting soil factors

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Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.80 - Herbicide-free agricultural methods (reduced-till, ground cover, soil-loosening)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

As in most European countries, soil erosion has worsened in Hungary in recent years. Although overall humus content has not fallen further in recent years, thanks to changes in tillage practices and the more widespread adoption of non-inversion tillage methods, this is only true on the gross average (https://www.biokutatas.hu/en/page/show/organic_nutrient_replenishment). In addition, halting the decline only means maintaining an already reduced level. It is therefore necessary to further develop and implement not only systems that aim to maintain current carbon levels, but also systems of soil (replenishment.https://www.biokutatas.hu/en/page/show/organic_nutrient_replenishment).

Examples: humus-preserving and humus-replenishing crop rotation in organic and conventional farming, with recommendations on which local plant species and varieties to use.

(https://www.biokutatas.hu/en/page/show/organic_nutrient_replenishment)

(In my opinion the text from the second sentence refers to Europe)

—

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

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Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

2 - Organic Farming

Other one (if any)

46 - No till

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P12 - Hungary (MTA ATK)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Yes
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Yes

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	early adopters
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	few farmers (“innovators”)

Specificities or further description of the practice

Activities

-The development of humus-preserving and humus-replenishing crop rotation in organic and conventional farming, as part of an on-farm research project, with recommendations on which local plant species and varieties to use;

-Establishing a ground-covering, mulch-based, sustainable tillage system, with particular focus on avoiding the use of indiscriminate herbicides, and integration into an organic farming system;

-Developing more effective applications of green-manure crops within open-field crop rotation.

The practice can be helped by the techniques of Solarvibes:

The aim of Solarvibes is to put technology into practice. This technology should be suitable for:

-Determining the temperature, pH, humidity, salt concentration and nutrient concentration of the soil.

-Using a smart phone app and artificial intelligence to assess the health of crops.

-Providing advice for farmers, considering the history of the soil and the effects of the surrounding vegetation.

-Optimizing the amount of input substances applied, as well as the timing of sowing, harvesting, and treatment with plant protection products. (<https://www.solar-vibes.com/>)

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	NA
Avoid acidification	NA
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	NA
Avoid salinisation	NA
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

This practice can be easily apply with soy beans, but for corn it's application is more challenging.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.82 - Use of microbial biofertilizers

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Biofertilizers are suitable alternatives for chemical fertilizers and are represented by organic waste (e.g., manure, compost, sewage sludge, and biodigestate), dead and living organisms (e.g., bacteria, fungi, seaweeds). Biofertilizers provide optimum nutrients for plant growth and favour an increase of soil biodiversity. Most of the microorganisms used for the preparation of microbial biofertilizers have symbiotic relationship with plants. Generally, biofertilizers are mainly used to supply nitrogen and phosphorus to plants. The use of biofertilizers represents an important component of sustainable agriculture (e.g., organic farming) because it is a viable alternative of chemical fertilizers, that are generally associated with various environmental negative impacts. Particularly, symbiotic microorganisms used as biofertilizers limit the environmental impacts because they fix atmospheric nitrogen and make it available in soil and root nodules of legume crops. Moreover, they can solubilize phosphate (from insoluble forms like tricalcium, iron, and aluminum phosphates) into available forms, sifting phosphates from soil layers. Biofertilizers favour the increase of crop yields due to nutrients availability and enhance soil structure, aggregates, and water retention, useful to increase root development and plant turgor.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Biofertilizers, bio inoculant
 - 2 microbial inoculum, seaweed inoculant

3	microbial preparations
4	mycorrhizal inoculant
5	compost, biodigestate

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

2 - Organic Farming

Other one (if any)

28 - Biochar

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P14 - Italy (CREA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected

Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Yes
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Mediterranean North (MDN)	early adopters
Mediterranean South (MDS)	early adopters
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The preparation of inoculum consists of several steps such as the inclusion of additives, selection of the best carrier, sterilization of carrier material, and adequate packaging with the best delivery method. The formulation process represents a crucial step in the production of biofertilizers because during this process it is important to maintain the viability of the used microorganisms and keep their activity at low levels. It is well-known that a good biofertilizer must be no toxic or pollutant, economically viable, favouring plant nutrient uptake to increase crop yields. Liquid and solid biofertilizer formulations exist and they can be applied as seed inoculation, root dipping, or directly on soils. So far, the production costs are high. An alternative approach to reduce the cost of producing biofertilizer is to use residues from agro-industry that are enriched with rock phosphate. The inoculation of crops with mycorrhizal fungi as biofertilizers is becoming more common because of the reduction in the population

of indigenous mycorrhiza fungi in the soil through the application of chemical fertilizer. Recently, new technology - involving the amendment of plant growth-promoting microbes with nanoparticles - has been introduced in the formulation of biofertilizer. The major challenges related to the application of microbial biofertilizer are: lack of awareness on the eco-friendly importance of microbial biofertilizer among the communities of farmers, inadequate promotion on the use of biofertilizer product to the farmers by the agricultural extension worker, lack of availability of suitable carriers for biofertilizer formulation, and lack of storage facilities to prevent contamination of the biofertilizer product.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Extreme climatic conditions can lead to inconsistency in the efficacy of biofertilizers on plant productivity in a natural environment. Soil should not be too dry or cold

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Adverse Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	No Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

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General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.83 - Soil drilling

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Drilling holes in compacted agricultural fields to counteract soil compaction, and to enhance the soil structure and water infiltration capacity.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Mechanic earthworm
2	
3	
4	
5	

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

18 - Deep rootening plants

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P2 - The Netherlands (WR)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not applied
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not applied
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Main characteristics & technical specifications:

The 'soil drill' is developed by Wageningen University & Research, as a measure to eliminate soil compaction. The installation is mounted on a tractor and drills holes through compacted soil layers, the holes having a diameter of 2cm at a spacing of 25x25cm or a diameter of 10cm at a spacing of 75x75cm. The holes are drilled through the compacted soil layer (usually at a depth of 35-45cm), at 50-60cm. Subsequently, the holes are filled with either sand on clay soils, or compost on sandy soils. Thereafter, a deep-rooting cover crop is sown, it is expected that its root system will grow through the columns and further reduces soil compaction.

Purpose:

The measure enables the elimination of place-specific soil compaction. The technique mimics the vertical tunneling activity of earthworms (*Lumbricus terrestris*). On clay soils, the sand columns function as a drain, improving the water infiltration capacity. On sandy soils, the columns filled with compost or a compost/sand-mixture facilitate root growth.

Activities:

The prototype has a width of 3m, when drilling at a spacing of 25x25cm, the practice requires a lot of time. In the (near) future, the practice might be automated. Apart from time, the 'soil drill' and sand or compost, the practice does not require specialized equipment or inputs.

Benefits/impacts:

A soil cultivator is often used to eliminate soil compaction, which can be seen as a short-term solution since such a practice leaves the soil sensitive to re-compaction. The 'soil drill' aims at a durable solution (~10y), and which, compared to a cultivator, causes less soil disturbance. Currently, the practice has been tested on several fields on clay, sandy and peat soils. The first results are promising.

Other:

The question is whether the practice is novel, as such or similar practices have been tested in Germany. However, the practice is not yet common and not included in the list of 58 practices, and therefore we decided to include the 'soil drill' in part III- innovative practices.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- wet soil conditions

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

- wet soil conditions: in case of clay soils, the soil needs to be dry to prevent soil slacking.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

The practice is in its experimental phase, currently being tested on several fields.

Limiting soil factors

- The practice aims at eliminating soil compaction, the practice therefore will be more successful on soils that are subject to subsurface soil compaction. Top soil texture does not limit the application, as the practice already has been tested on sandy, clay and peat soils.

Soil challenges

The practice is in the experimental phase: it has been tested and will be further developed. Researchers are currently evaluating the results, published research results are limited.

Impacts

The practice is in the experimental phase: it has been tested and will be further developed. Researchers are currently evaluating the results, published research results are limited.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.84 - Symmetrical mould-board plough without furrows

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The symmetrical mould-board plough (butterfly) is developed to facilitate shallow inversion ploughing in controlled traffic farming and prevent soil compaction.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Symmetrical mould-board plough
 - 2 Butterfly plough
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

41 - Controlled traffic farming

Other one (if any)

47 - On-Land ploughing

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P2 - The Netherlands (WR)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not applied
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not applied
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Characteristics & technical specifications:

The symmetrical mould-board plough is developed to combine inversion tillage with controlled traffic farming without the exchange of soil from the beds and the tracks. The symmetrical mould-board plough is able to cultivate a soil at a depth of 16cm. The instrument consists of two symmetrical rows with each three shares, distributing the soil via two channels to the rear end. In this way, the cultivated soil stays within the cultivation bed and does not end up on the tractor tracks. The equipment has a weight of 1200kg and costs around €23.000.

Purpose:

The symmetrical mould-board plough is developed to facilitate controlled traffic farming at a width of 3,15m and aims to prevent soil compaction.

Benefits/impacts:

The combination of conventional inversion tillage (with mouldboard plough) with controlled traffic farming led, in some cases, to in-field differences: the outside rows performed less than the inner rows, both in terms of soil structure and crop yield. The symmetrical mouldboard plough is developed to prevent cultivating the soil of the machine tracks and adding it to the cultivation bed. This should result in a better soil structure. The practice is currently being tested and further developed, no research results are available yet.

Farmers' opinions:

Especially for organic farmers the symmetrical mould-board plough is of interest, as it provides the opportunity to combine controlled traffic farming with tillage to control weeds.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Weather conditions required for this practice are similar to those required for conventional tillage.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

No (known) soil properties that limit the application of the symmetrical mouldboard plough compared to standard ploughing.

Soil challenges

As the practice is still in the experimental phase and still under development, the effects have not been scientifically tested. The effects indicated above are therefore expected effects, which have not been substantiated by research data.

Impacts

As the practice is still in the experimental phase and still under development, the effects have not been scientifically tested. The effects indicated above are therefore expected effects, which have not been substantiated by research data.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.85 - In-row fertilizer application

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

With in-row fertilizer application, nutrients are applied close to the crop roots, aiming at a higher nutrient use efficiency, reducing losses and higher crop yields.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Place-specific fertilizer application
 - 2 Combined sowing
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Not selected
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

30 - Inorganic fertilizers

Other one (if any)

33 - Organic fertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P2 - The Netherlands (WR)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	early adopters
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Characteristics & technical specifications:

With in-row fertilizer application, GPS is used to apply artificial fertilizer or slurry in rows where will be or have been sown. In-row fertilization can be done before or during sowing (usually at 5-8 cm next to the seed and at a depth of 5cm below the seed), or after (at a distance of 10cm). In-row fertilization during sowing is also known as ‘combined sowing’. In-row fertilizer in potatoes can be applied before planting; or between planting and ridging (pictures are available in Smit et al., 2013). In-row fertilizer application also allows split-applications.

Purpose:

The physical placement of fertilizers aims at an efficient nutrient use and to reduce the total amount of applied fertilizer.

Benefits/impacts:

Especially crops in the early stage, directly after germinating, and crops with a limited rooting system will benefit from nutrients that are directly available. As a result of both applying less fertilizer and enhanced nutrient uptake, nutrients are less susceptible to leaching. On clay soils, the application of slurry on potatoes before ridging provides flexibility for farmers, but also imposes risk of NH₃ volatilization and a lower nutrient use efficiency.

Farmers' opinions:

With strict fertilizer regulations, some farmers are worried about sufficient nutrient supply. The in-row fertilizer application is seen as a solution to meet the nutrient requirements (the right amount at the right time) of the cultivated crops. However, in practice is not yet common due to some practical barriers. When in-row fertilizer application is combined with sowing, machinery will be heavier, imposing a risk for soil compaction. Additionally, the combination is more labor-intensive, as less fertilizer can be taken into the fields and time is needed to refill (compared to applying fertilizer full-field without sowing).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

It might be more difficult to find the right moment to apply fertilizer taking into account the risk for soil compaction.

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No

2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	Beneficial Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

The effect of in-row fertilizer application (compared to full-field application) is expected to be larger in case of low (soil) temperatures in spring, and in cases of a suboptimal soil structure.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

In-row artificial fertilizer application is common in the cultivation of maize in the Netherlands.

Limiting soil factors

Limitations for in-row fertilizer application are not different than for the conventional full-field application.

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

Beneficial effects:

- The availability of nutrients increases
- Nutrients will be less susceptible to losses
- Crops will grow better at the early stage
- Reduce N and P fertilizer while maintaining yield levels

Both beneficial and adverse effects:

- Many research has been conducted on in-row fertilizer application, which led to variable results . Nutrient use efficiency and yields were strongly influenced by weather- and soil conditions.

Research has shown that the effectiveness of in-row fertilizer application is lower (compared to full-field application) in soils with high nitrogen and/or phosphate levels.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.86 - Cultivation of Marigold

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Different marigold species (*Tagetes*) can be cultivated to reduce the infection of some nematode species, such as *Pratylenchus penetrans*.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

1	Marigold
2	
3	
4	
5	

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected

Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

10 - Nematod protection

Other one (if any)

No data

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P2 - The Netherlands (WR)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	early adopters
Atlantic North (ATN)	early adopters
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Characteristics & technical specifications:

Marigold can be grown as a cover crop in between two main crops or as a main crop on infected soils. *Tagetes patula* is the most effective variety to reduce nematode infection, much better than *Tagetes erecta* and *Tagetes minuta*. For the marigold cultivation to be effective, an intense root system through the top soil is needed. Therefore, Marigold needs to be sown in May or June. The spacing must be 25cm at maximum, but a spacing of 10-15cm is preferred. About 5-10 kg of seeds needs to be sown at a depth of 0,5-1cm. Marigold requires N fertilization of around 50-75 kg N/ha.

Purpose:

The purpose of the marigold cultivation is to reduce the infection of nematodes, especially the infection of *Pratylenchus penetrans* and *Pratylenchus crenatus* have proven to be reduced after the cultivation of marigold. Furthermore, as Marigold is not a host for the below listed nematodes, the infection will reduce naturally:

- *Globodera rostochiensis*/*G. pallida*
- *Heterodera avenae*

- *Heterodera betae*
- *Heterodera carotae*
- *Heterodera schachtii*
- *Heterodera trifolii* f. sp. *Trifolium*
- *Meloidogyne chitwoodi*
- *Meloidogyne fallax*
- *Meloidogyne hapla*
- *Meloidogyne naasi*

Benefits/impacts:

The cultivation of marigold can completely eliminate the infection of *P. penetrans*, and the infection levels will be low for several years, even when host plants (such as potato) will be cultivated. The reduced levels of nematode infection, as a direct result of marigold cultivation, will benefit the crop yield of the subsequent cultivation of several main crops such as potato, flower bulbs and strawberry. For example, compared to fallow and other cover crops, significantly higher potato yields (8-14%) were reported when potato followed marigold. And compared to chemical soil fumigation, higher yields were reported for strawberries grown after marigold. Besides, marigold subtracts large amounts of N of the soil (~150 kg N/ha), the amount of N is strongly reduced at the end of the growing season, which prevents losses. The amount of N taken up by the plant residues will mineralize and benefit the subsequent crop cultivation.

Additional:

An European-wide tool with detailed information is available at Best4Soil.eu.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Yes:

- Soil moisture
- Soil temperature

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Yes, soil texture

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Soil moisture: a moist soil is required for a successful cultivation, in dry periods irrigation should be considered.

Soil temperature: Marigold is susceptible to temperatures below 0.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

Infection with *Pratylenchus penetrans* occurs in arable farming, olericulture, horticulture, flower bulb production and fruit production, and is therefore not relevant in grasslands (and silvopastoral systems). Literature regarding the cultivation of marigold to reduce nematodes in perennial cultivation systems such as olive groves is limited. It is possible that the presence of the roots of perennial crops is a permanent stimulus to maintain the growth of nematodes, limiting the effectiveness of this management practice in perennial cultivation systems.

Limiting soil factors

Infection with *Pratylenchus penetrans* mainly occurs on loam and sandy soils. Therefore, the effectiveness is limited to these soil types. However, Marigold can be grown for other purposes on other soil types, for example as cover crop aiming at organic matter production.

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

Positive:

- Marigold subtracts large amounts of N of the soil (~150 kg N/ha), the amount of N is strongly reduced at the end of the growing season, which prevents losses. The amount of N taken up by the plant residues will mineralize and benefit the subsequent crop cultivation.
- The reduced levels of nematode infection, as a direct result of marigold cultivation, will benefit the crop yield of the subsequent cultivation of several main crops such as potato, onion, maize and chicory.

Negative:

- As the development of Marigold is very slow, weed will develop quickly and might reduce the effectiveness. Therefore, weed control deserves serious attention.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.87 - Inundation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

With inundation, the soil is flooded for a period of time reduce the infection of nematodes.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Organic soil decontamination
 - 2 Anaerobic soil decontamination
 - 3 Flooding
 - 4
 - 5
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Not selected
Organic matter and nutrient management	Not selected
Tillage and traffic	Not selected
Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Not selected
Agricultural Systems	Not selected
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected

 NA

 NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

10 - Nematod protection

Other one (if any)

13 - Soil solarization

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P2 - The Nederlands (WR)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Yes
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Atlantic North (ATN)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

Characteristics & technical specifications:

Inundation is covering the soil with a layer of water, encouraging anaerobic bacteria to produce fatty acids, which kills almost all nematodes. Inundation is executed in a minimum of 10 weeks prior to planting in summertime. To start inundation, a small dike of approximately 30 centimeters high is created around a field. The field is continuously flooded with approximately 5cm of water, keeping the drainage closed and air free. To be effective, the field needs to be flooded for 10-14 weeks with a minimum temperature of 16°C.

Purpose:

This management practice aims at the reduction of pests and diseases, and in particular the infection of nematodes.

Benefits & impacts:

Inundation can control a number of soil-related diseases, pests, weeds and residues and is used as a sustainable method to control nematodes and some fungi. Inundation effectively reduces the infection of nematodes (*Meloidogyne fallax*, *Meloidogyne chitwoodi*, *Meloidogyne Hapla*, *Ditylenchus sipsaci*, *Pratylenchus penetrans*, *Globodera pallida*, *G. rostochiensis*,

Aphelenchoides subtennis, Rotylenchus and Trochodorus spp.) and fungi (Sclerotinia bulborum, Sclerotinia sclerotiorum Botrytis, Rhizoctonia tuliparum, Stromatinia gladioli, Phytium sp., Rhizoctonia solani, Sclerotium cepivorum, Fusarium sp. And Olpidium brassicae). The downside is that this can be a lengthy process, and farmers using this method may not be able to use their field for months.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Yes: <16 °C

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Uncertain
sloping (5-10%)	No
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

- Soil structure

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	No
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Adverse Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

Since soil bacteria, which are responsible for anaerobic conditions, are less active at low temperatures, soil temperature should be 16°C at minimum. With cooler soil temperatures, a longer period of flooding is needed.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

Inundation is more frequently used in the cultivation of flower bulbs. Inundation is expected not to be feasible in agroforestry systems, as many tree species are not resistant to flooding.

Limiting soil factors

Soil structure: the soil structure influences the time needed to reach anaerobic conditions, in sandy homogeneous soils, anaerobic conditions can be reached in only a few days.

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

Soil quality: studies have shown that soil properties such as texture, organic carbon, total nitrogen, pH, extractable phosphorus, potassium and clay content in periodically short-term (3-5 weeks) flooded soils do not decline. Long term flooding has proven to affect the macrofauna distribution in the soil and soil structure, as several species preferred periodically or episodically flooded locations. The effect on macrofauna has not been found in short-term inundation, however experience soil quality has never found to be improved after inundation.

The process is costly, the costs are around €2500-3000 per hectare.

The process is labour-intensive, as the field should be equalized, dams should be installed and the water level should be maintained.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.88 - Biochar

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Biochar is a solid material obtained from the thermochemical conversion of biomass in an oxygen limited environment. Biochar can be used as a product itself or as an ingredient within a blended product, with a range of applications as an agent for soil improvement, improved resource use efficiency, remediation and/or protection against environmental pollution, and as an avenue for greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

-
- 1 Biochar
 - 2 carbone vegetale (vegetal coal)
 - 3 biomassa di origine vegetale (vegetal biomass)
 - 4 NA
 - 5 NA
-

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Not selected

Crop protection	Yes
Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

2 - Organic Farming

Other one (if any)

34 - Use of biofertilizers

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and enviromental zone(s) initially reported

P14 - Italy (CREA)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Yes
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Not selected
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Yes
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Yes
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Yes
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	Not applied
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	NA
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not applied
Mediterranean North (MDN)	early adopters
Mediterranean South (MDS)	early adopters
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The name biochar refers to a “coal” derived from biomass thermal depolymerization processes. Thanks to its peculiar properties, it can be used to protect the environment and combat climate change.

The biochar obtained from the controlled pyrolysis of waste materials or food waste retains most of the carbon in a stable form, limiting its release in the form of carbon dioxide, limiting the emission of greenhouse gases and mitigating the phenomenon of global warming.

The particular surface structure of biochar, characterized by pores of heterogeneous dimensions and numerous functional groups and high surface area, makes it possible to use this material in the removal of organic and inorganic contaminants from water. It has a remarkable affinity with organic compounds such as pesticides, herbicides, dyes, which may be present in the run-off waters of agricultural land. If applied appropriately, in areas vulnerable to nitrates and within agricultural lands bordering the buffer strips, it has the ability to increase the activity of water purification and the action of removing pollutants. The biochar microstructure is an ideal environment for the growth of micro-organisms and when applied in the soil it causes an increase in microbial activity, aimed at making an effective contribution to reducing nutrient losses in water, sustainably from the environmental and economic point of view.

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors are not limiting. However, some authors suggest that soil temperature can increase biochar decomposition rate.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/gcbb.12266>

https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0038071714003496?casa_token=BILOyvfS7vQAAAAA:uHLpu504vowbxdpohPwy8ECwkypBMirevXOrMxcXfcEd2jsXB-OsYMIWGzcvWa6MOcrHEKP

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes – comment : Biochar can improve land productivity, sequester soil carbon, and mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emission. Particularly, on peatlands it can increase the growth and yield of rice plants. This aspect is not of particular interest for Italy where peatlands are very limited. However, it is important to mention the positive role of biochar to increase rice yield in Northern Italy.

<https://www.agronomy.it/index.php/agro/article/view/ija.2010.3>

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The high pH of biochar can limit its applications in semi- and arid soils. Therefore, application of biochar to agricultural soils in these areas are very limited. Soil pH is one of the major factors hindering the application of biochar to agricultural soils. Most types of biochar are of alkaline nature and its application to agricultural soil may negatively affect the availability of soil nutrients due to increasing soil pH. The pH of the produced biochar is a function of pyrolysis temperature and time; by elevating the pyrolysis temperature and time, the pH of the produced biochars can be higher than 8.5.

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain

Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Beneficial Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Beneficial Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	No Effect

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

/

Limiting soil factors

M.C. Andrenelli, A. Maienza, L. Genesio, F. Miglietta, S. Pellegrini, F.P. Vaccari, N. Vignozzi, Field application of pelletized biochar: Short term effect on the hydrological properties of a silty clay loam soil, *Agricultural Water Management*, Volume 163, 2016, Pages 190-196, ISSN 0378-3774, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.09.017>.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/ejss.13216>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167880919301082>

Soil challenges

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Impacts

/

Other general comments

- <http://www.refertil.info/>
 - <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7243815/pdf/peerj-08-9164.pdf>
 - <https://www.engineeringforchange.org/news/make-biochar-water-filter/>
 - www.ichar.org
 - <https://www.nerabiochar.com/en>
 - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265179>
 - <http://rifasa.it/home-page-en/>
 - <http://acchiappacarbonio.it/>
 - https://www.innovarurale.it/sites/default/files/2020-07/lineeguida5e_def.pdf (in italian)
 - <https://terraevita.edagricole.it/fertilizzanti-concimi/biochar-ammendante-sequestra-co2/> (in italian)
 - Ivano Vassura, Elisa Venturini, Alessandro G. Rombolà, Daniele Fabbri, Cristian Torri, Marco Errani, and Roberto Reggiani, “Biochar from gasification in cultivated soils and riparian buffer zones: Chemical characterization” in “Biochar: Production, Characterization and Applications”, Franco Berruti, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada Raffaella Ocone, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, UK Ondrej Masek, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK Eds, ECI Symposium Series, (2017). <http://dc.engconfintl.org/biochar/>
 - M.C. Andrenelli, A. Maienza, L. Genesio, F. Miglietta, S. Pellegrini, F.P. Vaccari, N. Vignozzi, Field application of pelletized biochar: Short term effect on the hydrological properties of a silty clay loam soil, *Agricultural Water Management*, Volume 163, 2016, Pages 190-196, ISSN 0378-3774, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.09.017>.
 - Latini, Arianna, et al. “A Narrative Review of the Facts and Perspectives on Agricultural Fertilization in Europe, with a Focus on Italy.” *Horticulturae* 7.6 (2021): 158.
 - Dal Ferro, N., Camarotto, C., Piccoli, I., Berti, A., Mills, J., & Morari, F. (2020). Stakeholder perspectives to prevent soil organic matter decline in Northeastern Italy. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 378.
-

References

Limiting climatic factors

/

Farming systems

/

Limiting soil factors

/

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

/

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

/

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	TRUE
Revised by authors	TRUE

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

B.89 - Roller Crimper

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The Roller crimper technique was developed by the Rodale Institute (Pennsylvania, USA) and is used to terminate a cover crop (mixture) in its generative, flowering phase. The roller crimper pushes the plants down and lightly crushes their stems, leaving a dead mulch layer on top of the soil.

Locally used names, synonymes or aliases

—
1
2
3
4
5
—

Land management category

Crops and Crop rotation	Yes
Organic matter and nutrient management	Yes
Tillage and traffic	Yes
Crop protection	Not selected

Water Management	Yes
Agricultural Systems	Yes
Buffer strips and small landscape elements	Not selected
NA	NA

Practice in inventory A linked to this innovative practice / experience

Main one (if any)

1 - Conservation Agriculture

Other one (if any)

39 - Conservation tillage

DETAILED INFORMATION ON THE PRACTICE / THE EXPERIENCE

Country and environmental zone(s) initially reported

P4 - Belgium (Flanders) (ILVO)

Alpine North (ALN)	Not selected
Alpine South (ALS)	Not selected
Anatolian (ANA)	Not selected
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Yes
Atlantic North (ATN)	Not selected
Boreal (BOR)	Not selected
Continental (CON)	Not selected
Lusitenean (LUS)	Not selected
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	Not selected
Mediterranean North (MDN)	Not selected
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Not selected
Nemoral (NEM)	Not selected
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	Not selected

Application rate of the practice in environmental zones (inside the country)

Alpine North (ALN)	NA
Alpine South (ALS)	NA
Anatolian (ANA)	NA
Atlantic Central (ATC)	few farmers (“innovators”)
Atlantic North (ATN)	NA
Boreal (BOR)	NA
Continental (CON)	NA
Lusitenean (LUS)	NA
Mediterranean mountains (MDM)	NA
Mediterranean North (MDN)	NA
Mediterranean South (MDS)	NA
Nemoral (NEM)	NA
Pannonic-Pontic (PAN)	NA

Specificities or further description of the practice

The Roller crimper technique was developed by the Rodale Institute (Pennsylvania, USA) and is used to terminate a cover crop (mixture) in its generative, flowering phase. The roller crimper pushes the plants down and lightly crushes their stems, leaving a dead mulch layer on top of the soil. After mulching the cover crop the main crop is sown or planted throughout the mulch layer. Crimping has to be done at late flowering in order to obtain enough biomass (5 to 6 ton DM/ha) to suppress weeds (UNL, 2019).

The usage of a roller crimper leads to a longer growing period of the cover crop which allows for more carbon sequestration (ILVO, 2018) and a shorter fallow period (oral communication by Koen Willekens 2022, researcher at ILVO). Since the cover crop is entirely incorporated into the mulch, the loss of carbon and nutrients is very limited. This leads to an organic matter build-up which in its turn may stimulate soil life (oral communication by Koen Willekens 2022, researcher at ILVO).

Multiple years of using the roller crimper may stabilize the soil structure which increases its carrying capacity and decreases the risk of compaction (ILVO, 2018). A further advantage is that mycorrhizae that live in symbiosis with crops are sustained outside of the growing period thanks to the continuous input of nutrients (oral communication by Koen Willekens 2022, researcher at ILVO).

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climate factors

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Site and soil factors

Slope gradient classes?

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown – comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land use and farming systems

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	No

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	NA

Other impacts

Impacts on crop yield	Unknown Effect
Impacts on farm profitability	Unknown Effect
Other Impacts (add comments in the next question)	NA

COMMENTS, REFERENCES AND OTHER INFORMATION

Comments on previous data

Limiting climatic factors

During dry summers there might be insufficient biomass production from the cover crop to get a mulch layer that is sufficiently weed suppressing.

Farming systems and potential area of application of the practice

A roller crimper can be applied in certain terrace farms on the condition that the area of the terraces is large enough.

Limiting soil factors

Less productive soil might be a problem when these do not allow for enough biomass production of the cover crop.

Soil challenges

/

Impacts

Crop yield depends on the crop type: it works on the condition that the C stock in the soil is already sufficiently high. If this is not the case than the use of a roller crimper might jeopardize the crop yield.

Other general comments

/

References

Limiting climatic factors

paste here

Farming systems

paste here

Limiting soil factors

paste here

Soil challenges

paste here

Impacts

paste here

General references and documents, doi, website, url,...

ILVO. (2018). No-till beheer van groenbedekkers en toepassing van de roller crimper. [online]:No-till beheer van groenbedekkers en toepassing van de roller crimper - ILVO Vlaanderen.

University of Nebraska-Lincoln (UNL). (2019). A roller-crimper for cover crop termination and weed suppression. [On line]: A Roller-Crimper for Cover Crop Termination and Weed Suppression | CropWatch | University of Nebraska–Lincoln (unl.edu)

Information on sources

Sources used for filling this part of the survey

/

Documentation and pictures available in shared folders (internal use of the EJP Soil only)

Documentation

- No documentation

Pictures

- [empty] ...

Other document that can contain pictures and/or information (‘.docx’)

- [empty] ...

Videos files

- [empty] ...

Other information on pictures and videos (‘.txt’)

- [empty] ...

NOTES ON THE STATUS OF THIS ENTRY

NA = no information (maybe revised)

Reviewed by coordination	TRUE
Reviewed by other partners	NA
Revised by authors	NA